

Late Antique Basilicas on Cyprus

sources, contexts, histories

3: Gazetteer

Richard Maguire 2012

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Cyprus: the Late Antique Basilicas

In addition to relative importance, the length of entries represents availability of publication, access and condition. Basilicas are described even where, as in Chapters 3 and 5, there may be overlap with the main text. For descriptions of the baptisteries at Agios Epiphanius, Ayios Philon Ayia Trias and Kourion and the apse mosaics at Lythrankomi, Kiti and Livadia the reader is referred to Chapters 3 and 4 respectively. Where basilicas have been understood as a group, (Aphendrika, Kalavastos and Peyia) or are in close proximity (Amathus, Kourion, Paphos, Polis, Salamis) bibliographies appear at the end of the section.

Catalogue number	1	Location	Akamas (Ακάμας)	Map reference	34.52.30 N 32.33.15 E
Identification/ dedication	Ayios Kononas	Date	Late 5th early 6th c	District	Paphos

Hogarth described ‘the ruins of the village [which] seem to be no older than the churches, and are probably Byzantine. Gunnis wrote that ‘At Agios Konon are the ruins of a large town about a mile and a half inland from the sea.’ Ayios Kononas is not attested in any written source.

The site was first excavated in 1989 and the earliest exposed structure was a villa of the 340s. Around 400 a number of small farmsteads formed the nucleus of a new settlement which flourished in the later fifth- and early-sixth centuries and thereafter declined. The site was abandoned about 800.

Basilica of Ayios Kononas

The three-aisled basilica, c.13.7 x 21.7m, was constructed entirely from local materials. It concluded in the east with a single apse, four-sided on the exterior and circular on the interior, and was preceded in the west by a narthex [1.1]. The arcades were supported on four columns assembled from stone drums capped by variously decorated limestone

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capitals [1.2]. Three portals opened in a west wall constructed from large blocks of limestone quarried only 30m from the site. Two surviving jambs probably indicate a doorway at the east end of the north aisle. The extent to which the bema projected into the nave is unclear as its furnishings were removed to a position west of their original location. The excavators suggest that extensions of the bema into the eastern bays of the aisles may have served as pastophoria (cf Kourion). The chancel screen was carved from Lefkara chalk with an openwork décor of circles and crosses and the posts capped with pinecones [1.3]. Much of the floor was bedrock but the east end was paved with gypsum. Mouldings, identical to those at Peyia led Fejfer and Hayes to suggest that, c.600, the same workshop was active at both sites.

Bibliography

ARDA	(1990) 63-64; (1991) 62-3; (1992) 62
Åstrom	(1992) 68; (1995) 67
BCH	(1990) 983; (1991) 829-31 fig. 54; (1992) 828-30, figs 80-81
Fejfer and Mathiesen	(1991) 211-223; (1992) 67-83
Fejfer and Hayes	(1995) 62-69
Gunnis	(1936) 382
Hogarth	(1889) 13
Megaw	(1974) 70
Meyza	(1995) 187 pl. 2
Procopius/Dewing	(1971) 361
Rautman	(2000) 325
Roberts	(2000) 51
Wallace	(1984) 341-347

Catalogue number	2	Location	Akanthou (Tatlisu)	Map reference	31.25.20 N 29.56.33 E
Identification/dedication	<i>Panagia Pergamieniotissa</i>	Date	6th c.	District	Famagusta

The basilica lies on the north coast 4.5km northeast of Akanthou, close to the site of the Hellenistic and Late Antique settlement of Pergamum. In 1972 excavations to the east and north of the middle Byzantine church which now occupies the site revealed substantial parts of a three-aisled, tri-apsidal basilica orientated 15° north of east, the remains of which extended about 3.5m eastwards from the later church, the northeast quoin of which may have been built on the stylobate of the Late Antique basilica [2.1]. A springer to the north west of the present church suggests that the basilica had arcades supported on limestone columns [2.2-3]. The plan of the south apsidiole is well preserved. A section of straight wall at its north end together with the southeast

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respond of the nave arcade located c.0.55m from this wall must have belonged to an inter-apsidal passage with, probably, a corresponding passage to the north [2.4]. A passageway of this width is at the lower end of the scale but comparable with Aphendrika-Asomatos [2.5]. A synthronon may have been inserted in the sixth century, making the passageways redundant. There was a step between the north apsidiole and the north wall effecting a transition from the lateral walls to the thicker apse walls suggesting that they carried semi-domes. An unidentified structure was set against the middle of south apsidiole [2.6].

Bibliography

ARDA	(1972) 13
Chotzakoglou	(2008) 114-115
Hadjisavvas	(1991) 7-8
Papacostas	(1999) II 64, III 210

Catalogue number	3	Location	Akrotiri (Ακρωτηρι)	Map reference	34.35.00 N 32.56.45 E
Identification/dedication	Katalymmata ton	Date	Early 7th c	District	Limassol

The excavation of the only transeptual building on the island, Structure A, was completed in 2009 and the excavation of the remainder of the site, under Procopiou, is on-going [3.1]. Structure A together its east wing, excavated in 2010-11, is an unusually large structure at a time when, with the possible exception of the Acropolis Basilica at Amathus, smaller buildings were the norm [3.2].

The overall plan consists of three squares of approximately 12m by 12m – the division marked by columns at the inner ends of the ambulatories lining the walls of each transept arm. A bema projected eastwards from the west wall of the transeptual building.

Constructed of rubble in poured gypsum plaster, its walls were approximately 0.50m thick. There were five apses, one in the middle of the north and south walls and three in the west wall. The walls of the central apse, semi-circular on the interior and five-sided exterior, were approximately 1.00m thick and the four apsidioles, semi-circular inside

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and out, were c.60m thick, suggesting they carried semi-domes [3.3]. The size of the gold, glass and mother-of-pearl tesserae found in the destruction layer of the central apse suggest that its semi-dome was decorated with mosaic [3.4]. The apsidioles in the west wall were biased towards the central apse at 9.5m centres. All the apsidioles were approximately 2m wide suggesting a funerary context. This hypothesis was strengthened by three finds: (1) a small hipped-roofed marble sarcophagus lid with *akroterion* and a funnel at the apex was discovered in the southeast corner of the south transept in 2008 [3.5]; (2) in 2009 the remains of a Proconnesian *mensa martyris* were excavated in the southwest apsidiole: a funnel pierced the centre of the *mensa* which was connected by means of a terracotta *cataract* probably to a reliquary located beneath it (cf the *mensa martyris* in the south apsidiole of Agios Varnavas) [3.6] and (3) in the south apsidiole, also in 2009, a full-sized, hipped-roofed sarcophagus lid was excavated. It had *akroterion* at the corners with a large cross the full width of the lid, the centre of which was pierced by a funnel [3.7]. The larnax was constructed from separate limestone slabs and contained the skeletal remains of a male, his head toward the west, together beads, a pin and coins from the first decade of Heraclius' reign. The lid was clearly *in situ* before the construction of the apsidiole because its southern *akroterion* were embedded in the apse wall. The apses in the north transept have been located, but they provided no further evidence, given a significant fall in the surface level resulting in a much poorer state of preservation.

Two 2.5m-wide ambulatories linking the apsidioles lined each transept arm [3.8]. It is possible that transverse arches distinguished the north and south aisles of the ambulatories given the discovery of two Proconnesian marble plaques with foliate décor which probably served as the 'capitals' of the pilasters receiving the arch in the southwest corner of the south transept. The ambulatories were continuous with the aisles of the east wing while, to the west, they concluded against the bema. Procopiou argued that the ambulatories were barrel vaulted given the lack of nails and organic material indicating wood. Numerous tiles fragments, however, suggest a timber-framed roof certainly over the 6m-wide span of the spaces enclosed by the ambulatories. There is evidence for additional, non-bonded buttresses in the south transept - at the northeast outer corner, in the middle of the east wall and in the southwest inner corner [3.9]. These probably supported vaults and a gallery given the discovery of marmara and Proconnesian flooring slabs in the destruction layer.

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Proconnesian marble posts supporting gypsum screens surrounded the *mensa martyris*. The bema, too, was surrounded by rubble and poured plaster posts supporting closure screens at least one of which was a Proconnesian marble panel with a décor of a pierced wreath and a knotted ribbon with trails ending in hederas supporting crosses. No altar has thus far been identified. The bema was approached through a short solea the panels of which were laid directly on the mosaic pavement.

The floors were mosaic throughout, varied in their geometric décor and remarkably well preserved [3.10-11]. The floor of the apse retains the impression of what may have been a synthronon [3.12] although there is no further supporting evidence given the area has been entirely robbed. The lack of mosaic pavement either side of the bema suggests bema may have carried clergy benches which Megaw understood as predating the introduction of synthronona. There are figurative elements in the mosaic pavement in front of the bema but the most striking imagery is on the bema itself including two deer with a vine rising from an acanthus whose branches are filled with birds pecking grapes. This was preceded by a transverse carpet with a pelta décor and a larger carpet with a meander motif. The north and south arms of the transept were treated somewhat differently – on the north more glass was used and the motifs were more complex but the reason for the difference is unclear.

The décor of the walls was probably sumptuous; small pieces of yellow Italian marble, one representing a hand, almost certainly belong to an *opus sectile* figure (cf Pezia). Plentiful evidence of marble plaques suggests that the lower walls were revetted while surviving plaster fragments makes it likely that the upper walls were painted. The interior was lit by *polykandelon* and from window openings of glass set in a gypsum lattice. Fragments of offering tables were recovered in some quantity.

The wing extending eastwards from Structure A consisted of a nave and aisles together with a long corridor-like annex to the north [3.13], together with a series of ancillary spaces to the south. The nave and aisles, too, were paved with mosaic including two inscriptions intended to be read facing west. An atrium was attached to the east wing the peristyle of which was marmara paved. Investigations in the area of the atrium suggest that there were no previous buildings on the site.

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Bibliography

ARDA (2006) 92-3; (2008) 67-69; (2010) 58-60
Heywood in Swiny (1982) 162
www.mcw.gov.cy

Catalogue number	4	Location	Akrotiri, (Ακρωτηρι), Lania	Map reference	34.34.38 N 32.59.45 E
Identification/dedication	Unknown	Date	5th-7th c?	District	Limassol

Late in 1995 and early in 1996 the Department of Antiquities conducted excavations in two subterranean chambers on the British base at Akrotiri under Procopiou's direction. Carved into the bedrock, both were orientated north-south and entered from the north. Each consisted of a nave and aisles prefaced by an ante-chamber. The central nave of Basilica I was 23 x 11.5m and Basilica II was 17 x 13m, with a maximum height of about 3m. Instead of columns the aisles were divided by carved piers. In Basilica I the roof was completely preserved with one large light-well and five smaller ones. The floor of Basilica II contained ceramic inclusions from the fifth to seventh centuries. Their function remains uncertain.

Bibliography

ARDA (2003) 48
BCH (1997) 902-3 figs 47-9
Heywood (1982) 162

Catalogue number	5	Location	Alassa (Αλασσα)	Map reference	34.45.51 N 32.55.39 E
Identification/dedication	Ayia Mavri	Date	Early 7th c	District	Limassol

In the mid-1980s rescue excavations connected with the construction of the Kouris dam revealed several Late Antique and earlier structures 750m east of the village of Alassa. [5.1-2]. Dated by ceramic and numismatic evidence to the seventh century, the basilica of Ayia Mavri was excavated by Flourentzos in three campaigns between 1984 and 1986. Its life must have been short because the church and village were destroyed by fire in the mid-seventh century.

Basilica

The basilica probably had three aisles with a single apse, of which only the narthex, nave and a north aisle survive [5.3-5]. Given the number of roof tiles it is assumed that the building was timber-roofed. The entrance appears to have been from the north into the narthex through a 1m-wide portal, on the evidence of an internal threshold in mosaic, 0.30 x 0.72m, filled by a guilloche and an apotropaic eye [5.6].

Part of a seventh-century geometric mosaic pavement in rather large tesserae, extended into the narthex and the north aisle (now in the grounds of Limassol Castle). The 7 x 2.5-metre-long north aisle was arranged in two panels [5.7]. At the east end the design consisted of an open field with small squares and circles with cruciform centres. At the west end a panel with a red denticulated frame was filled with a lattice motif. At the junction of the narthex and the north aisle was a much damaged and probably dedicatory inscription of eight lines in a 1.17m circle. The first line had the initials ΙΗΣΟΥΣ ΧΡΙΣΤΟΣ, ie. (IC+XC) with a cross in the centre, the second line had ΠΡΟΝΟΙΑ followed by a cross and the third line was largely illegible [5.8]. The north end of the narthex was paved with a décor of squares and the south end with circles and semi-circles arranged to form a lattice and framed with a guilloche.

The south aisle may have been destroyed during the construction of a road to the village. The nave is 11.50 x 5m with two pairs of internal buttresses; of the mosaic floor that probably paved it, nothing survives. The apse, which Flourentzos supposed to have been horseshoe-shaped, was probably crowned by a semi-dome. It is ashlar faced on the interior but its exterior is imbedded in a mass of probably later masonry [5.9]. The arcades were carried on columns with simplified Doric capitals. The incised blocks built into a pier on the south side of the nave probably served as imposts for the arch of the semi-dome of the apse [5.10]. The remains of what may be the site of the altar projected 3.5m from this apse, broadly aligned with the eastern pair of internal buttresses. Of the annexes attached to the west of the narthex, the northernmost was probably an *apanteterion*.

Numismatic evidence dated to Heraclius and Heraclius Constantine between 629 and 640 establishes a *terminus post quem* for the destruction of the site by fire. A slab from one of the annexes bears Heraclius' monogram, together a Θ referring to the regnal year

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9 suggesting imperial influence c. 618/9. Given the building was restored and used to at least to 641 Flourentzos assumed the settlement was strategically important. However, Papacostas points out that there were no major routes in the vicinity and that it is more likely that, being at the confluence of two rivers, there would have been abundant irrigation for a small farming community supplying Kourion some 13km away, hence the decline of Alassa may have been linked to the decline of Kourion.

Bibliography

<i>ARDA</i>	(1985) 36-9; (1986) 60-62; (1987) 44-5
<i>BCH</i>	(1985) 897-967
Flourentzos	(1996)
Papacostas	(1995) 5-7 Gazetteer 7; (1999) I.39

Amathus: Introduction

After Salamis and Paphos, Amathus was the island's third city. Its acropolis was occupied by a celebrated temple to Aphrodite. In the fifth-century a Bishop Tykhon requisitioned the temple for Christian worship, expelling its priestess with the aid of a whip. The first bishop was Mnemonios and its second was an earlier Tykhon, (d.c.402-408). John the Almsgiver, the seventh-century patriarch of Alexandria, the son of the island's governor and author of a *Vita* of Tykhon, was born in Amathus. John was reputedly interred at Ayios Tykhonas in the middle of the three apsidal tombs on the north side of the church. In the seventh century the temple of Aphrodite was dismantled to provide the building material for the construction of a basilica on the acropolis. However, the life of this basilica would have been brief. In 649 the Arabs torched the Acropolis and overran the city despite its impressive fortifications.

There are the remains of five basilicas in or close to the site, the Acropolis basilica, the southwest basilica, the basilica dedicated to Tykhon, the Episcopal basilica and, further east, the basilica of Ayia Varvara.

Catalogue number	6	Location	Amathus (Αμαθούς)	Map reference	34.42.51 N 33.9.10 E
Identification/dedication	Acropolis Basilica	Date	Late 6th – early 7th c	District	Limassol

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Rather than being preceded by an atrium the basilica occupied the northeast quarter of a vast walled enclosure, 60 by 46m [6.1]. Discovered in 1984, the three-aisled basilica was oriented 25° north of east, possibly to take advantage of a site which dominated the valley below [6.2]. Numismatic evidence suggests a date towards the end of the sixth century and the beginning of the seventh. The basilica appears to have been built in a single campaign on a site not otherwise associated with Christian worship.

The aisles were divided by a 0.30m high stylobate capped with marble slabs, which carried four black bases on each side, bearing Proconnesian (?) columns which carried an arcade ending, east and west with pilaster responds [6.3]. There was, however, no stylobate at the west end where the westernmost bay constituted a transverse corridor.

Of the five apses probably constituting a *coup d'oeuil* from the valley below only three belonged to the basilica proper. The central apse was five-sided and the apsidioles were three-sided [6.4]. Of the two annexes attached to the north aisle, the easternmost ended in an apse, horseshoe-shaped on the interior and three-sided on the exterior. A portico attached to the south of south aisle extended eastwards ending in a rectangular annex that may have been the site of an earlier apse.

The central apse was filled with a marble-revetted, synthronon, possibly with an episcopal throne [6.5]. The probable position of an ambo (0.55m. x 0.55 m.) in the northeast corner of the nave is unique on the island [6.6].

The bema (4.5m x 6m), defined by a barrier at bay 4, did not extend into the aisles but was accessed from them and from the nave. It was paved with large pieces of Proconnesian marble except for a slab of green breccia (1.5m x 0.5m) forward of the apse, marking the position of the altar [6.7]. The discovery of a column suggests that the altar may have been covered by a ciborium, corresponding to the canopy on columns covering the large octagonal *phiale*, (4m. x 4m. x 5m. deep), the only feature in the walled enclosure with which the basilica was aligned.

Of the three aisles, the nave, the south aisle and all the apses were paved in *opus sectile* [6.8]; the north aisle (13m x 3) was paved with gypsum slabs and a bench ran along its north wall [6.9]. The nave floor was divided into three longitudinal fields with sixteen subsections [6.10-11]. The semi-circle of the apse of the northeast annex was paved in

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black and white marble, green schist and spoliata pilaster champlevé capitals laid flat in a circular arrangement [6.12]. Tesserae found in the main apse indicate that its upper walls and/or semi-dome were decorated with mosaic. Fragments of red and green painted plaster suggest the walls may have been painted. The precinct was paved in irregular limestone slabs sealing all trace of the previous structures on the site.

Benches were a commonplace in the ancillary rooms but it is not clear which, if any, served as the *katechumenaion* [6.13]. The apsidal annex attached to the north aisle was the most likely site for a baptistery, although it could have served equally well as a treasury. Offering tables have been identified in the apses of the north and south aisles. The large number of annexes suggests they may have served as accommodation perhaps in connection with a pilgrimage circuit of the basilicas in the immediate vicinity.

A narthex 12.2m x 4.9m in the west was preceded by a 24.8m-long exo-narthex, effectively a continuation of the south portico turned at right angles. A further portico on timber supports, which was itself a continuation of the exo-narthex, lined the northwest side of the atrium and continued along much of the southwest wall. Three further annexes extended northwards from the narthex, two extended northwards from the exonarthex, three lay behind the northwest arcade and one was set in the angle of the northwest and southwest porticoes of the atrium. There were galleries over the aisles and the narthex.

Reconstructions suggest that pent and gabled roofs rose tower-like over the nave. The overall plan of the basilica, together with its immediate annexes was almost square at 25m x 24 m. with the nave and aisles forming a 13m square, presaging the taller, more compressed proportions of Middle Byzantine churches [6.14].

Catalogue number	7	Location	Amathus (Αμαθούς)	Map reference	34.41.34 N 33. 1.31 E
Identification/dedication	Ayios Tykhonas	Date	Late 4th – early 5th c.	District	Limassol

This extra-mural basilica was orientated 5° south of east. The late 14th and early 15th century remains shelter one of the earliest buildings on the island; an upper church of the second half of the fifth century built over a lower church ascribed by numismatic evidence to the late-fourth century, ie to the episcopate of Mnemonios and Tykhon [7.1].

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The lower church had an almost square plan with a western corridor [7.2] with a recess in its west wall [7.3] (cf Toumballos). To the east there was a single apse, circular on the interior and polygonal on the exterior [7.4]. In the interior the very short nave was divided from the aisles by piers. To the south a pastophoria-like annex projected east of the chord of the apse but nothing remains of a comparable arrangement on the north where a 2m thick wall may have been inserted to support the upper church at a point where the land falls steeply away.

The upper church of c.450-500 overflies the lower church, the east end of which it substantially repeats [7.5]. Also divided by piers into a nave and aisles, the upper church extended westwards, further in the nave than in the aisles [7.6]. There were no western entrances; rather the main entrance appears to have been in the middle of the south wall aligned with the easternmost of the three adjacent, north-facing apses outside the church to the north [7.7]. The easternmost of these was marble lined and the remaining two were vaulted [7.8]. According to Leontios of Neapolis Tykhon was buried here shortly after 400 and John the Almsgiver in 620 - perhaps the powerful *locus sanctus* for pilgrims accommodated in the Acropolis basilica. The upper church too was clearly conceived as a funerary basilica incorporating the burials of the lower church as well as *ad limina* and extra-mural burials immediately to the west. It may have served as the funerary church of the Amathusian bishops given the discovery of a seal of Bishop Theodorus (c.600-650). Unlike the Acropolis basilica numismatic evidence suggests that the building was in use until the end of the seventh century.

Catalogue number	8	Location	Amathus (Αμαθούς)	Map reference	34.42.48 N 33.9.43 E
Identification/dedication	Episcopal Basilica	Date	Second half of 5th c	District	Limassol

The basilica is orientated 5° north of east. The sea has encroached from the south and more than half the nave and the whole of the south aisle are missing. The 30m-long basilica originally consisted of three aisles and a triapsidal east end, the apses semi-circular inside and out [8.1-3]. Seven columns on limestone bases, with Theodosian capitals of Proconnesian marble, divided the nave from the aisles [8.4]. Further west lay a narthex and an atrium [8.5] surrounded by further ancillary rooms with evidence of benches [8.6]. A marmara-paved corridor ran the entire length of the north aisle

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possibly serving as a *katechumenaion* and there is some evidence for a similar arrangement on the south. Aisles, nave and narthex were floored in *opus sectile*. The complex was damaged during the second Arab raids of 653/54.

Catalogue number	9	Location	Amathus (Αμαθούς)	Map reference	34.42.47 N 33.9.10 E
Identification/dedication	Southwest basilica	Date	5th c	District	Limassol

This three-aisled, tri-apsidal basilica lies at the foot of the south slope of the Acropolis [9.1]. Its northwest corner of the basilica was rock cut to a height of 2.5m which may account for its orientation 20° north of east. It was excavated under Nicolaou between 1965 and 1966 and subsequently under Papageorghiou. Its three-aisled interior 20m x 12m [9.2] was preceded by a narthex with benches against its west wall. A narthex with benches in such a constrained site suggests that here the narthex may indeed have served as a *katechumenaia*. A raised exo-narthex, 11.00m x 2.7m, replaced the usual atrium, accessed through what the excavators describe as a ‘funerary room’ [9.3]. The three apses were semi-circular on the interior and polygonal on the exterior [9.4]. Marble columns were set on a raised stylobate and carried Theodosian capitals in finely-worked local stone. Their irregular spacing suggests trabeation rather than arcuation. The raised bema closed in the east with a synthronon. The altar table, forward of the apse, was supported on five pillars [9.5]. The cornices of the basilica carried stucco reliefs of dogs chasing does, (cf the ‘Huilerie’ at Salamis and Kalavassos) and the walls were decorated with a combination mosaic and painted plaster. Floors were lime mortar except in the bema which was paved with *opus sectile* (cf Acheiropoietos at Lambousa and the Baptistery Basilica and Limeniotissa at Kourion). Attached to the south of the church was an apsidal-ended room, 15.5m x 2.75m [9.6]. To the north of the north aisle an annexe may have served as a *skeuophylakion* or *diakonikon*. The basilica originally dates from the fifth century; some columns were replaced with piers in the later seventh.

Catalogue number	10	Location	Amathus (Αμαθούς)	Map reference	34.42.52.N 33.9.4.E
Identification/dedication	Ayia Varvara	Date	6th c.?	District	Limassol

To the east of a cemetery and at the foot of the Vikles Hill, the basilica was built around the entrance to a grotto dedicated to St Barbara. The complex consists of a small five-

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aisled basilica, with four apses [10.1]. Substantial evidence remains for its funerary function including tombs above and below pavement level [10.2-3]. Amongst the scant remains of mosaic paving is an inhabited trellis [10.4] and a pavement of poised squares [10.5]. Fragments of marble offering tables and a chancel screen with a chi-rho were also recovered from the site. A marmara paved court west of the basilica led to some 17 additional rooms suggesting that the complex may have been monastic [10.6]

Bibliography

- AJA (1967) 404
ARDA (1966) 13; (1967) 14; (1975) 29; (1976) 30; (1977) 36; (1985) 52-3; (1986) 50; (1987) 51-2; (1989) 45-6; (1991) 48-9; (1998) 64-7, 76-8; (2003) 41; (2003) 47-8; (2003) 50-1
Aupert (1996a) 161-65; (1998)
BCH (1962) 412; (1966) 386; (1967) 363; (1975) 836; (1976) 888-891; (1977) 720, 763-765; (1980) 805-822; (1981) 1025-34; (1982) 745-751 (1983) 955-969; (1985) 975-981 figs 17-26; (1986) 881-899 figs 3-37; (1987) 741-754 figs 18-36; (1989) 860-871, 994 figs 9-27; (1990) 992-4; (1991) 751-759 figs 1-23; (1994) 485-90; (1995) 705-09
Gunnis (1936) 208-210
Hermery (1984) 276-7
Michaelides (1987b) 49Papacostas (1999) II 78
Papageorghiou (1986) 502
Pliny/Rackham (1942) 319
Pralong (1994) 211-14
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Aphendrika Introduction

The Karpas Peninsula has some of the best stone on the island. On the north coast, northeast of Rizokarpaso, and 1.5km west of the site of ancient Urania, two basilicas stand 30m apart - Panagia and Asomatos. Hogarth described the churches as Byzantine, Gunnis and Enlart as Romanesque. However, Megaw's 1946 article, 'Three Vaulted Basilicas in Cyprus,' decisively proved that the buildings belonged to more than one period, the earliest of which was Late Antique. Both were timber roofed, three-aisled, columnar basilicas with triapsidal east ends, the apses of which were semi-circular inside and out and were connected by barrel-vaulted interapsidal passages, of which the northern one survives at Aphendrika and both survive at Asomatos. Both had broadly similar proportions and their marble fittings suggest a sixth-century date.

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Catalogue number	11	Location	Aphendrika	Map reference	35.38.50 N 34.26.28 E
Identification/ dedication	Asomatos	Date	6th c.	District	Famagusta

Asomatos (the ‘incoporeal’) had a proportion of 1:2.73, an external dimension of 19m by 12.5m (240 sq.m.) [11.1-3]. The nave was 5m x 15m and the aisles were c.2.5m wide. They were divided by five relatively short stone columns, c 2.4m high, set c.2.4m apart on multi-stepped bases about 0.50m square [11.4] and topped with capitals with two large torus mouldings with alternating steps and filets, the whole raised on a stylobate 0.72m across [11.5]. A respond in the form of a demi-shaft, bonded with the masonry of the apse, survives at the east end of the south wall [11.6]. Several column drums, also about 0.5m in diameter are reused in the foundation of the later north wall [11.7].

A small step effects the transition from the thinner lateral walls and the 0.55m thick walls of the three apses [11.8]. Sixth-century wallwork remains in the southwest corner of the building where the ashlar is laid side-alternate fashion, and at the southeast angle of the nave where the wallwork is not bonded with the later south wall. There are no rebates for doors which led Enlart and Jeffery to conclude that there would have been a narthex, although neither drew the same conclusion in respect of Aphendrika.

The inter-apsidal passages, between 0.50-0.55m wide, are remarkably well preserved and comparable in width with those at Pergameniotissa [11.9]. The main apse was filled with a synthronon that cut across the apse rather than followed its curve. It consisted of at least three steps with a narrow axial projection [11.10]. A small recess in the south apsidiole was possibly used for sacramental vessels, suggesting that the end of the south aisle could be closed off [11.11]. The chancel was probably enclosed by screens and panels given the stone post built into the upper south wall of the nave, the incised décor of which is comparable with the treatment of the posts of the solea at Ayia Trias [11.12]. The post led Papageorghiou to conclude that Asomatos pre-dated the large-scale import of marble.

Catalogue number	12	Location	Aphendrika	Map reference	31.25.20N 29.56.33E
Identification/ dedication	Panagia	Date	6th c.	District	Famagusta

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The basilica was orientated 5° north of east [12.1-2]. Measuring approximately 25m x 15m, it had a proportion of 1:2.85 and an external area of 475 sq.m.. Its 7.8m-wide nave was divided from the aisles by 7 columns with intercolumniations of 2.77m, concluding east and west with responds in the form of demi-columns. At the west end of the south arcade and at the east end of the north these demi-columns in part survive [12.3]. One column, 0.54m in diameter, remaining from the Late Antique basilica has almost certainly been resited to support a failing arch. There was no narthex. The surviving south wall provides evidence for a building of local limestone in alternating headers and stretchers, the decorative qualities of which would almost certainly have been intended (cf Soloi) [12.4-5]. At only 0.50m the walls would have been insufficient to carry a vault and these had to be strengthened with an additional skin on interior in the aisles and on the exterior of the apses. The sizes of the windows too were radically reduced when the vaulting system was introduced [12.6]. The apses were constructed in twin stretchers and headers and carried semi-domes [12.7]. The north apsidiole is the best preserved: socket holes in its southeast quadrant suggest that the apse could be closed off perhaps with a combination of rails and drapes [12.8]. Of the two inter-apsidal passages, that on the north is preserved almost intact [12.9]. The central apse was lined with a synthronon. [12.10]

The hypothesized lateral projections immediately preceding the north and south apsidioles shown in Megaw's plan are omitted from Stewart's on the basis of Papageorhiou's cleaning of the site in the 1960s.

Amongst the furnishings recovered were fragments of a marble ambo, a capital and a column base. The seating for the closure screen of a bema, used in a later church on the site, may have belonged with these original furnishings. [12.11].

Bibliography

Enlart	(1987) 306
Jeffrey	(1918) 258
Megaw	(1946) 49-54
Papacostas	(1995) Gazetteer 2; (1999) II 10-11, 17; III figs 34, 61
Papageorhiou	(1965) 94; (1993) 42; (1996) 221
Sotirou	(1935) 13a
Stewart	(2008) 43

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Catalogue number	13	Location	Ayia Moni	Map reference	34.53.57 N 32.37.8 E
Identification/dedication	Ayia Moni	Date	5th -6th c?	District	Paphos

A basilica was constructed here in Late Antiquity is now wholly concealed by later structures with the possible exception of the 'many large blocks conspicuous among the small rubble' identified by Hogarth [13.1].

Bibliography

Grishin	(1996) 50-52, 70n 140
Hogarth	(1889) 31-35
Jeffery	(1918) 391-92
Mitford	(1961) 105-7
Papacostas	(1999) II 39, 97; figs 122-24
Papageorghiou	(1965) 97
Stylianou	(1957) 68-70 n.133

Catalogue number	14	Location	Choirokoitia (Χοιροκοιτία)	Map reference	34.47.47 N 33.20.11 E
Identification/dedication	Panagia tou Kambou	Date	Late 6th c/ early 7th c	District	Limassol

The building was three-aisled with a central apse and inscribed apsidioles [14.1]. To north and south there were ancillary rooms of which those to the south may have been funerary.

Bibliography

www.mcw.gov.cy

Catalogue number	15	Location	Episkopi (Επισκοπή)	Map reference	34.43.47N 33.0.54 E
Identification/dedication	Saraya	Date	Late 7th early 8th c	District	Limassol

Episkopi lies 1.5km east of Kourion. This small three-aisled, tri-apsidal basilica was oriented due east [15.1]. Its importance lies in the *spolia* brought largely from the bema of the Episcopal Basilica at Kourion when that building was dismantled and finally abandoned during the course of the 8th century. The basilica probably also served as the

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new seat of the bishop. Excavated champlévé marble fragments include an acanthus scroll frieze and several panels with a medallion inscribed in a lozenge. Furthermore, a section of paving at Sarayia was composed of sections which fitted the dimensions of the north aisle at Kourion exactly. One champlévé fragment comes from an ornate pilaster which may have stood at south side of the entrance to the apse of the Episcopal basilica. Other fragments probably originated from the bema floor which had been stripped to its foundations [15.2]. Michaelides records Megaw as claiming that there was a floor under the present floor at Episkopi and similar to it.

Bibliography

ARDA	(1979) 38-9
BCH	(1979) 722 fig.98; (1980) 803 fig. 102
Boyd	(1989) 1821-41
Megaw	(1993) 53-67
Michaelides	(1993) 78 and n. 50; (1998) 206-207
Papacostas	(1995) Gazetteer 7; (1999) II 28
Solomidou-Ieronimidou	(1989) 167-170
Young/Swiny	(1982) 151-159

Catalogue number	16	Location	Germasoyeia (Γερμασογεια)	Map reference	34.40.60 N 33.4.60 E
Identification/dedication	Kalogeroi (Elijah)	Date	No data	District	Limassol

Excavations around the visible remains of the apse were conducted by Procopiou in 2001. This timber-roofed basilica was 19m long (excluding the polygonal apse) and 8m wide. It is rare on the island in being single-aisled. The bedding for floors, the foundation of the synthronon and the position of the chancel screen has been identified. The discovery of ash in some quantity suggested to the excavators that the building was destroyed by fire. There were traces of additional structures to the northwest and to the south which, given that the toponym *Kalogeroi* means monk, may have been monastic quarters for which the basilica served as the *katholikon*.

Bibliography

ARDA	(2007) 71
DOA	(2001) Press Release, MXK/NX

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Catalogue number	17	Location	Geronisos	Map reference	34.53.57N 32.18.41E
Identification/ dedication	No data	Date	No data	District	Paphos

A small basilica was identified at the east end of the island most of which is now lost in the sea. It has been described as ‘a partner to the three basilicas that sit just opposite on the mainland.’

Bibliography

Connelly (2002) 245-268; (2005) 149-181; (2010) 295-348
www.mcw.gov.cy

Catalogue number	18	Location	Geroskipou (Γεροσκηπου)	Map reference	34.45.31.N 32.27.9.E
Identification/ dedication	Agioi Pente	Date	5th-7th c	District	Paphos

Evidence for Late Antique occupation came to light in November 2002 during road works. Excavated under Michaelides, the basilica, orientated 45° south of east, which once dominated the site, has almost completely disappeared. Its inscribed apse [18.1] and the compartments either side of it received burials. The variety and quality of the imported marbles - columns, offering tables, marble revetment, champlévé panels, as well as, mosaics and painted plaster - attest to an impressive structure. Ancillary rooms north and west suggest a monastic context. A marmara-paved court to the east of the basilica was surrounded by a number of mosaic-paved rooms, one of which covered a burial, the first discovered under a mosaic pavement in a non-basilical setting on Cyprus. One mosaic floor survived complete with three medallions containing inscriptions from the Book of Psalms. An extensive burial complex was associated with the basilica which possibly occupied the site of a necropolis. It included tombs lined with Proconnesian marble and one slab pierced by a funnel [18.2]. The complex survived to the period of the Arab incursions.

Bibliography

ARDA (2005) 77-79; (2006) 83-4
Michaelides (2004) 185-98
www.mcw.gov.cy

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Catalogue number	19	Location	Gialousa (Sipahi)	Map reference	35.33.10 N 34.13.80 E
Identification/dedication	Ayia Trias	Date	Early 5th c	District	Famagusta

Excavation was begun by Dikigoropoulos and completed by Papageorghiou, who dated the building to c.425 on the style of the mosaics and the discovery of a coin of Honorius (395-425). This three-aisled, tri-apsidal, columnar and galleried basilica was oriented 10° north of east [19.1-4]. Dedicated to the Holy Trinity, it was a 13.7 m long, (17.3m including the apse), the nave was 6.9m wide and the overall proportion was 1:2.51. In common with the much later basilicas of the Karpas group, a step effected the transition from the 0.55m-thickness of the lateral walls and the 0.80m-thick apse walls. Five limestone columns with intercolumniations of 2.88 were set on a stylobate dividing the nave from the aisles [19.5]. Their capitals carried a simple moulding comparable with Soloi B. The raised sanctuary extended about one-and-a-half bays into the nave and was reached by two steps [19.6-7]. Megaw suggested that the bema carried clergy benches. No trace survives of sockets or grooves for a screen on the bema itself but the intercolumniations corresponding to the bema appear to have been infilled with a stone screen [19.8]. An independent stone solea, nearly 9m in length, occupied the centre of the nave [19.9]. Its posts were 0.17m deep and 0.20m on the face and because they broke through the mosaic floor it is assumed that the solea was a later addition [19.10]. The stone screens, however, sat directly the pavement [19.11]. The décor of the pierced screens and the posts was inscribed rather than sculpted. There is no indication of the height of the panels or posts and no evidence for an ambo.

The basilica was preceded by a narthex which doubled as the fourth side of an atrium which gave access to a number of ancillary rooms. The narthex closed in the south in a room with an inscribed apse which was entered from the north through a trilebon rebated for a screen. The north end of the narthex, however, appears to have ended in a rectangular room [19.12]. The addition of ancillary spaces to the north and south of the aisles, and extending the full length of the basilica, would have given an east end consisting of projecting main apse, apsidioles and straight shoulders comparable to Agios Epiphanius, Chrysopolitissa and Soloi [19.13]. The west end of the annex attached to the south aisle possibly served as a *katechumenaia* given the benches against its

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north and south walls. The east end provided access from the baptistery (described in Chapter 3) where a doorway into the south aisle was probably used by the newly baptized approaching their first communion. This route was barred when the east end of the corridor was converted into a chapel [19.14].

The mosaic floors of the complex largely survive. Two inscriptions in the nave pavement gave the name of the mosaicist or donor. The first was immediately inside the west doorway [19.15] and the second, biased toward the south, formed part of the border immediately in front the raised sanctuary [19.16]. The mosaics of the nave were laid out as three rectangular concentric frames. The first framed the whole nave and the final one was occupied by the solea [19.17]. The outer frame was geometrical, including panels particularly at the east end, which may have been schematic representations of marble in graded bands of four tesserae alternately mono- and polychrome. The next frame had diagonal crosses made from spindles the arms of which had an imbricated or pelta infill [19.18]. The inner frame consisted of a poly- and monochrome T-meander surrounding a processional way of intersecting circles [19.19].

The aisles were treated differently from one another; the mosaic in the south aisle was a continuous carpet of squares and poised squares containing a variety of cross motifs including loosely tied figures of eight, Solomon's knots and groups of four ivy leaves [19.20]. The north aisle was divided into seven sections [19.21] - from west to east, (1) a pattern of alternately horizontal and vertical double-axe heads (2) a panel including a pomegranate and two pairs of sandals [19.22] (3) a panel of intersecting circles (4) a panel of fan-shaped imbrication surrounded by a *hedera rinceaux*, (5), two transverse bands; (a) alternating circles and diamonds and (b) an open simple guilloche, (6) alternating squares and poised squares and (7) vertical and horizontal double axe-heads surrounded by a single open guilloche. The raised stylobates may also have been decorated with mosaic; see, for example, the westernmost intercolumniation on the south side [19.23].

The apsidal-ended room at the south end of the narthex had a floor of alternating larger and smaller circles containing poised squares in an undulating *hedera* border. In the centre of the narthex, but off axis, a large circle filled its width almost entirely [19.24]. A star inside the circle was formed from eight lozenges infilled with alternating pelta and spindle variants [19.25]. The carpet to the south of this circle was framed with a

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guilloche-within-a-guilloche in the centre of which was a panel of alternating squares and poised squares joined by 8-armed stars. To the north of the circle there was a strip of guilloche-within-a-guilloche, then a panel of two large crosses containing poised squares with spindle trelliswork.

The mosaic pavement of the southern entrance to the complex leading to the south portico of the atrium was given a particularly rich treatment, including a hedera border east and west and a panel of interwoven circles to the north [19.26]. The south end of this panel had a guilloche-filled swastika meander more complex, but similar to, the sanctuary floor of Basilica A at Soloi, the complexity of which was doubtless apotropaic. The design extended northwards to encompass a square panel with multiple borders, the centre of which is unfortunately missing. The basilica may have been destroyed during the Arab raids of the mid-seventh century.

Bibliography

<i>AJA</i>	(1967) 403-4, pl.117, fig. 20
<i>ARDA</i>	(1958) 17; (1964) 14; (1966) 13; (1967) 14; (1971) 23; (1972) 24
Dikigoropoulos	(1957) 50
Megaw	(1974) 67
Megaw/Du Plat Taylor	(1981) 233, n.8
Papageorgiou	(1964) 372-74; (1966) 159-60

Catalogue number	20	Location	Gialousa (Yeni Erenköy)	Map reference	No data
Identification/dedication	Chtomólia	Date	No data	District	Famagusta

A mosaic pavement was discovered in trial excavations undertaken by Dikigoropoulos for the Department of Antiquities in 1957 about 1.5km north east of Ayia Trias. It confirmed the existence of a small three-aisled basilica with a single apse. Five stone columns flanked the nave with evidence for galleries over the aisles. Two more columns separated the narthex from an apsidal chapel to the south. The mosaics were bordered with guilloche and ivy-leaf motifs.

Catalogue number	21	Location	Gialousa (Yeni Erenköy)	Map reference	35.35.9 N 34.18.32 E
Identification/dedication	Agios Fōtios	Date	6th Century	District	Famagusta

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A few metres to the west of the Middle Byzantine church the northeast quadrant of an apse survives [21.1]. Running north-south and forming a tangent with the curve of the apse is a straight wall of the same construction – headers and stretchers c.50cm high. Papacostas is of the view that the Middle Byzantine church was built over the Late Antique basilica and indeed the foundation another apse survives aligned with the east end of the church [21.2].

Bibliography

Chotzakoglou (2008) 120-121
Papacostas (1999) II 69, III fig 225
Soteriou (1935) pl 40b

Catalogue number	22	Location	Golgoi (Αθιενου)	Map reference	35.4.0 N 33.32.60 E
Identification/dedication	Unknown	Date	No data	District	Larnaca

A small basilica was discovered in 1972 [22.1].

Bibliography

AJA (1973) 429
Bakirtzis (1976) 260-266
Papageorghiou (1993), 28 n. 10
Pliny/Rackham (1942) 129-131, 319

Catalogue number	23	Location	Dali (Δαλι)	Map reference	35.01.30.N 33.35.30.E
Identification/dedication	Idalion	Date	No data	District	Nicosia

Basilica located but not excavated.

Bibliography

Papageorghiou (1993) 28

Kalavastos-Kopetra: introduction

The site was identified in 1978 and excavated 1989-1991 under Rautman. Three broadly contemporary basilicas lie in close proximity on a bluff on the east bank of Vasilikos River about 2km south of Kalavastos and about 4km north of the anchorage at Zygi-Petrini. The settlement of *Kopetra* dates to c.400, with a major expansion in the 6th century so that by the mid-7th c its population had risen to about 100 families (pop. 500-600). A thriving economy was based on mining and agriculture, particularly olives. Imports included fabrics from the Aegean and North Africa and ceramics from Syria and Palestine.

Kopetra-Sirmata was about 200m to the east of Area II which was south of Area V. While each basilica marked an approach to the settlement Areas II and V were earlier and more fully integrated into the settlement. All three were three-aisled triapsidal columnar basilicas: the apsidioles of *Sirmata* and Area II were mural and only Area V had three projecting apses. Walls and columns were constructed from fieldstone in poured gypsum plaster, the raw materials for which were available close to the site. The columns were rendered and painted in imitation of marble. Marble itself was reserved for the most important of fittings, with stucco used for the remaining embellishments. Rautman suggested the use of ‘itinerant craftsmen’ for the mosaics in the bema of Area II and the stuccowork, given that wooden-mould-cast capitals at *Kopetra* were comparable to those at Huilerie at Salamis. Red roof tiles came from as far as Paphos in the west and yellow roof tiles from the Mesaoria to the east.

Catalogue number	24	Location	Kalavastos (Καλαβασος)	Map reference	34.45.19 N 32.59.29 E
Identification/dedication	Area II	Date	Late 6thc - Early 7thc	District	Limassol

Area II was aligned with *Sirmata*, some 200m to the west. Both were about 20° north of east and on approximately the same axis [24.1]. The basilica was 18m long by 9m wide with a nave 4.5m wide, terminating in an apse 3.6m wide [24.2]. The apsidioles were mural [24.3] and the central apse was curved on the interior, polygonal on the exterior and lined with a bench [24.4-5]. The five columns of the colonnades had

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intercolumniations of c.2.75m, terminating east and west with engaged demi-columns. Three doorways connected the basilica with the narthex. A doorway at the west end of the south wall led to a lateral annex, contemporary with the core of the building, and extending almost the entire length of the south aisle and concluding in the east with an apse round on the interior and, according to Rautman, polygonal on the exterior, although the individual faces are no longer discernible [24.6]. Its floor level was 0.50m below that of the basilica and it was lined with low benches suggesting that it may have served as a *katechumenaia*, although, there is no evidence for a baptistery. An additional room occupies the space between the central apse and the lateral annex [24.7]

The bema, 3.66m by 5.03m and 0.40m above the pavement, extended two bays into the nave. There is no evidence for the kind of lateral extension into the aisles found at broadly-contemporary Peyia. It was paved with a geometric mosaic of alternating squares and circles carried out in black, white, light blue-grey, pink and red-stone tesserae. The panel was surrounded by a double border, one of lozenges and the other with a double-stranded guilloche. The floor of the remainder of the basilica was paved with well-cut gypsum slabs. Tesserae found in the eastern part of the church - blue, green, yellow, red, white, grey, black, of stone and glass and some with gold foil caps - suggest that walls and/or the semi-dome of the apse were decorated with mosaic. There is abundant evidence of the use of stucco. The columns defining the bema, for example, appear to have had spirally fluted while those corresponding to the nave had vertically fluted shafts, both capped by acanthus capitals also in gypsum plaster. Fragments of moulded lettering from a large inscription also survive together with a relief with a bird and a small relief of an enthroned Theotokos with Christ on her lap. There was some imported marble including the rim of what was probably an offering table.

Catalogue number	25	Location	Kalavassos (Καλαβασος)	Map reference	34.45.22 N 33.18.30 E
Identification/dedication	Area V	Date	Mid 7th c.	District	Limassol

Area V is 250m to the north of Area II and about 275m north-east of *Sirmata*. The three-aisled basilica with three projecting apses, probably round, inside and out was preceded by a narthex [25.1]. An annex was attached to and ran the full length of the south aisle. Partly excavated, nothing now remains above ground. Area V is closer to the relative

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opulence of Area II in its use of gypsum mouldings, possibly some Proconnesian marble and, evidence for *opus sectile* [25.2-3]. The semi-dome of the main apse probably carried a mosaic decor.

Catalogue number	26	Location	Kalavassos (Καλαβασος)	Map reference	34.45.19 N 32.59.29 E
Identification/dedication	<i>Sirmata</i>	Date	2nd half 6th c.	District	Limassol

Situated on a marl knoll this small basilica was orientated 20° north of east [26.1]. Stratigraphy suggests that *Sirmata* was one of the last projects undertaken in the Vasilikos valley. The complex consisted of a timber-roofed, columnar basilica, with an apse [26.2] and mural apsidioles and, to the north, a court with ancillary buildings on the west and north. The nave was divided from the aisles by four columns and, in the west, by a rectangular pier with attached demi-columns, of which those on the west corresponded to half-shafts against the west wall. These defined a broad transverse aisle that may have been reserved for a congregation, given that the ancillary buildings suggest a monastic context

The columns of the nave were c.0.50m across with intercolumniations between 2.3 to 2.5m, a variation suggesting that the colonnades were trabeated. The nave, 19.0m long and 5.0m wide, was accompanied by aisles 1.8m wide. The raised bema projected two bays into the nave and its kerb probably carried a chancel screen. An altar base (1.21 x 0.92m) was set into the paving in front of the apse and a three-tier synthronon with projecting axial steps lined the apse wall [26.3]. The excavators suggest that two holes drilled at the ends of its second tier may have provided the anchors for the chancel screen. A second base, similar to that of the altar found to the southwest of the bema may have supported an offering table. Décor was austere in comparison with areas II and V with little evidence of marble and stucco and no surviving evidence of *opus sectile*, mosaics or painting.

The narthex measured 11.5m by 3.4m and its floor was 0.53m below that of the basilica from which was accessed with the aid of a step running the entire length of its east wall. There was one doorway into the narthex and three from the narthex into the basilica, a central doorway of 1.60m and two of 1.20m. The narthex was articulated by demi-columns which marked two equal bays, north and south, and a central double bay

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[26.4]. The northern and southern bays corresponded to the extensions to the narthex, but the inner double bay was smaller than the width of the nave, hence the demi-columns in the narthex and those against the west wall inside the basilica were out of alignment. The narthex projected 2m beyond the north and south walls of the basilica. Aligned with its south extension were two rooms which together probably extended along the entire south flank of the basilica. The easternmost room may have been a mortuary chapel and if the westernmost annex served as a *katechumenaia*, excavation has yet to reveal a baptistery. An L-shaped bench lined the northwest corner of the narthex [26.5] and its southern extension accommodated a subterranean chamber, certainly contemporary with the basilica, 2.00m deep, 3.4m east-west and 2.4m north-south (cf Peyia south). Reached by a flight of six stairs [26.6], it contained two tombs constructed from gypsum slabs set against its east and south walls; the east tomb served as an ossuary and contained the remains of five individuals and the south tomb contained the remains of two adults and an 11-year-old child.

A doorway in the north wall [26.7] of the basilica led to an open court, 12.5m east-west and 8.5m north-south, attached to the north of the basilica and c.1.00m above its floor level. Atria are widespread throughout the island but atria to the north were relatively rare. The court was entered from the east. A 2.2m square block of rubble and gypsum, probably associated with later use of the site, was set skewed at the approximate centre of the court and there was a 3.5 metre deep circular cistern in its southeast corner in which were found the remains of 3 adults, 6 children, a horse and one or more dogs. Sixth and seventh centuries ceramic finds, together with the fact that *Sirmata* appears not to have been subject to repair, suggests a brief life brought to an end by a fire sometime between 600 and 650 which also damaged Area 2.

Bibliography

ARDA	(1990) 55-6; (1991) 54, 60-61; (1992) 60-1
Rautman and McLellan	(1990) 231-5
ARDA	(1989) 50-1; (1990) 55-56; (1991) 54; (1992) 60-1
BCH	(1991) 10-12, 814; (1992) 812-13
Papacostas	(1999) II 49, III 157
Papagorghiou	(1986), 492-93
Rautman	(2000) 317-331, (2001) 307-318, (2004) 189-217, (2006) 453-463
Rautman and McClellan	(1989) 157-166; (1989-90) 14-29; (1990) 231-238; (1991) 225-236; (1994) 289-93
Stewart	(2008) 32

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Catalogue number	27	Location	Karpas	Map reference	35.36.22 N 34.23.40 E
Identification/ dedication	Ayios Philon	Date	Early 5th c. Early 7th c.	District	Famagusta

The Karpas Peninsula, the islands ‘pan-handle’, was probably the most densely populated part of Cyprus in Late Antiquity. Karpasia was a port city situated on the north coast of the peninsula. Numismatic evidence suggests occupation from 408-666. Hill suggested the second invasion of Mu’āwiya in 653/4 for the abandonment of the site but Dikigoropoulos, based on numismatic evidence, proposed a date not earlier than the garrisoning of the island by the Arab invaders in 669. Some time after 620 the settlement was provided with new fortifications and, on the basis of a coin found under one of the *opus sectile* floors, the episcopal complex too appears to have been renovated at about the same time. The two moles enclosing the harbour were assembled from ashlar blocks, c.0.50 x 0.50 x 1.00m, laid on bedrock and held together with swallow-tailed lead cramps.

Basilica

In plan Ayios Philon is close in to the Aphenrika group and may have been their prototype [27.1]. Like them it lay close to Rizokarpaso to which the see was probably transferred after the abandonment of the site in the seventh century. Ayios Philon is mentioned as an Episcopal see c.325 although no bishop is recorded before Philon who, according to the *Vita* of Epiphanius, was consecrated c.382 by his friend the Bishop of Salamis. Hence, Philon was active around 400 and it is quite possible that he was the church’s founder and perhaps the architect of what has been described as the smallest Episcopal basilica on the island, built at a time when Episcopal basilicas were being constructed on vast dimensions. Here the maximum length was 20.80m and its maximum width was 13.40m. At c.308 sq.m the internal area of Ayios Philon was barely an eighth that of Agios Epiphanius at 2436 sq. m.

The complex was probably approached directly from the harbour [27.2]. The three-aisled, triapsidal basilica was preceded by a narthex and a three-sided colonnaded atrium now lost to the sea. The basilica was orientated 3° north of east and the baptistery (described in Ch.3) immediately to the south was orientated 15° north of east, the difference possibly being accounted for by earlier structures on the site. The

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complex was constructed piecemeal; the basilica and the baptistery from selected ashlar and properly mortared while the remainder of the buildings were constructed from material from other parts of the site and included column bases, mortared together with mud or gypsum.

Stone stylobates divided the nave from the aisles, each supporting bases, columns and capitals of the same dull yellow, breccia-type marble, probably imported as set from Asia Minor. The acanthus capitals were more naturalistic in treatment than the norm a century later, which the excavators, du Plat Taylor and Megaw, suggested, may have been finished off locally. Seven columns with intercolumniations of c.2.20m created an exceptionally close spacing suggesting trabeation rather than arcuation. The colonnades supported galleries over the aisles and concluded with pilasters at the west end and demi-columns at the east. The stylobate does not appear to have extended to the westernmost bay where, on the north side at least, it was replaced at pavement level by an *opus sectile* threshold (c.f. Amathus, north basilica at Peyia, Kourion baptistery basilica). At the east end of the basilica narrow transverse passages probably linked the three apses (cf Agios Epiphanius, Soloi, Lambousa, Aphendrika, Asomatos, and Pergameniotissa). Small steps articulated the transition from the thinner lateral walls and the thicker walls of the east end and the excavators surmised that the large number of tesserae found dumped in the baptistery may once have been used in the decoration of their semi-domes. The apses were semicircular inside and out, the central apse springing not from the east wall but from some distance inside it. The northernmost apsidiole was almost horseshoe shaped in plan [27.3]. A terracotta sarcophagus (1.85 x 50 cm) discovered at the east end of its north wall suggests that that part of the building may have constituted a martyrial focus. Megaw proposed apsidal-ended corridors attached to the sides of the basilica north and south and serving as *katechumenaia*.

The synthronon which once lined the apse was certainly a later addition because it rendered the inter-apsidal passageways unserviceable. Surviving marbles suggest that the altar was covered by a ciborium and that the bema was surrounded by posts and closure screens. An ambo of the bridge type with opposing staircases (cf Campanopetra and Peyia) was set on axis in the nave.

The *opus sectile* paving of the principle areas may belong to the comprehensive renovation of the site probably around the first quarter of the seventh century when the

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narthex and the basilica were paved in *opus sectile* [27.4-5]. A doorway at the south end of the narthex led to the corridor running between the basilica and the baptistery, which, together with the area immediately outside the western entrance to the baptistery, was paved with marmara suggesting that both areas were covered by porticoes.

The second and larger atrium was probably the near contemporary of the basilica given the coin of Arcadius (395-408) discovered under the floor of its east range. Its east portico lacked a rear wall but rather opened directly onto an *opus-sectile*-paved extension of the passageway immediately to the east of the baptistery [27.6]. In the centre of the atrium was a 1.40 metre-wide *phiale*, circular on the interior, hexagonal on the exterior, tanked in hydraulic plaster and revetted in Proconnesian marble [27.7]. The *phiale* was surrounded by a shallow drain and a wide pavement consisting of six trapezoids framed in Proconnesian marble and filled with *opus sectile*, in various designs.

What might have been purpose of a second atrium apparently contemporary with the first? Was it on axis with a large building to the east for which the *opus sectile* corridor identified above served as a narthex [27.8-9]? Might such a solution explain the row of piers with demi-shafts on their south faces which define a narrow corridor, 1.5m across and open at its west end, remarkably similar to the piers with attached shafts which defined the outer corridors at Agios Epiphanius? Where this to be the case Philon may have designed a much larger basilica (probably as wide as 24m) than the one which, at present, bears his name – a building closer in scale and design to the Episcopal basilica of which his friend Epiphanius may have been the architect.

Bibliography

Cobham	(1908) 316
Dikigoropoulos	(1940-48) 98
Gunnis	(1936) 413-4
Hackett	(1901) 320, 381
Hill	(1940) I, 285
Hogarth	(1889) 90
Jeffery	(1918) 254
Megaw	(1974) 64; (1997) 343-352
Megaw/du Plat Taylor	(1981) 209-250
Papacostas	(1995) Gazetteer 4; (1999) II 65-6, III fig 313-15
Papageorgiou	(1966) 244; (1985) 323; (1986) 500 ; (1993) 41
Soteriou	(1935) pls.10b, 14

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Catalogue number	28	Location	Kellia (Κελλία)	Map reference	345832 N 333720 E
Identification/dedication	Agios Antonios	Date	5th c	District	Larnaca

Of the 5th century basilica little remains beyond the groundplan of the triapsidal east end with some vestigial wallwork at the junction of the central apse and the south apsidiole [28.1-2]. The apsidioles were semi-circular internally and externally. The main apse was polygonal although later repairs have obscured the articulation of its faces. The walls of the apsidioles were 0.65m thick with 1.40m internal width. The main apse was not less than 0.90m thick and approximately 10m across externally. A chancel-screen post decorated with vine scroll in Limassol Castle survives from the bema.

Bibliography

Gunnis	(1936) 261-2
Jeffery	(1918) 193-4
Papacostas	(1999) II 8, 143; III figs 26-30
Wharton	(1988) 56

Catalogue number	29	Location	Kiti (Κίτι)	Map reference	34.55.2 N 33.35.50 E
Identification/dedication	Angeloktistos	Date	5th, late 6th / 7th c	District	Larnaca

The basilica is orientated 10° north of east. What had probably been a fifth-century, three-aisled triapsidal basilica was rebuilt as a timber-roofed pier basilica after a fire in the late sixth or seventh century incorporating the apse of the earlier basilica, probably together with its synthronon [29.1]. There is evidence that the first basilica was embellished with a stucco décor given the gypsum respond against the east wall in the form of a plaster-carved acanthus capital. Megaw and Hawkins believed that the apse originally lacked a décor, having been discoloured by fire before the addition of the plaster of which the acanthus capital forms a part. The mosaic in the semi-dome of the apse, in which the Virgin and Child are flanked by two angels, is described in Chapter 4. A spirally-fluted black column, probably of Troad granite, a stone column and a Proconnesian chancel screen post in the vicinity of the basilica may have been part of the fittings of the columnar basilica. [29.2-3]

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Bibliography

<i>BCH</i>	(1960) 295-7, fig. 75
Dikigoropoulos	(1961) 186-205
Enlart	(1987 ed) 334-5
Foulias	(2006)
Gunnis	(1936) 272-3
Jeffery	(1906) 485, (1918), 185-7, 261
Karageorghis	(1960) 296
Megaw	(1960) 350-1, 74-76; 19, (1974), 74-76, (1985) 173-98 at 184-192
Megaw/Hawkins	(1977) 31, n.127; 121
Papacostas	(1999) II 6, 144; III figs 18-22

Catalogue number	30	Location	Knidos	Map reference	35.19.45 N 34.1.45 E
Identification/dedication	No data	Date	6th c?	District	Famagusta

Basilica located but not excavated.

Bibliography

Goodwin	(1984) I.483
Papageorghiou	(1993) 28

Kourion

The site was excavated by Pennsylvania University under McFadden from 1934-35, by the Department of Antiquities between 1956 and 1959 and by Dumbarton Oaks under Megaw between 1974 and 1979.

The city, which suffered severely during the earthquakes of the late fourth century, was rebuilt at the beginning of the fifth and the Episcopal basilica belonged to that campaign. The basilica was intentionally dismantled sometime after 670 – dated on the basis of a solidus of Constantine IV (668-673) found in a floor deposit related to the last use of the covered cistern in the south-west court. Megaw suggested that the failure of the water supply may have initiated the relocation to Episkopi. Material from the basilica continued to be salvaged into the eighth century

Bishop Zeno of Kourion represented the Church of Cyprus at the Council of Ephesus in 431 and, according to Megaw, his authorship of the basilica accords with the

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archaeology. Given the Council's formulation in favour of the Theotokos we might speculate that Marian imagery played a significant part in the basilica's lost decorative scheme.

Catalogue number	31	Location	Kourion	Map reference	34.40.23 N 32.53.16 E
Identification/dedication	Baptistery Basilica	Date	Early 5th c to early 7th c	District	Limassol

The Baptistery basilica is described in Chapter 3.

Catalogue number	32	Location	Kourion	Map reference	34.39.54 N 32.53.16 E
Identification/dedication	Episcopal Basilica	Date	Early 5th c.	District	Limassol

The basilica was built on the remains of what was probably a Constantinian civic basilica which substantially affected on the layout of the whole complex [32.1-2]. A street running north-south limited the complex's eastern extent and the cliff edge limited its western extent, hence a monumental axial approach through an atrium was impossible. The major entrances appear to have been through the atrium in the northwest corner of the complex [32.3-4] and a propylaeum off-set to the north of the corridor dividing the baptistery from the basilica [32.5].

The nave of the three-aisled galleried basilica ended in an apse, circular on the inside and polygonal on the outside [32.6]. The twelve columns on either side of the nave were all Roman *spolia* [32.7]. The colonnades terminated east and west with demi-columns. The aisles ended in rectangular pastophoria (rare on the island) [32.8-9] which were accessed through tribela, the capitals of which took the form of marble plaques assembled in pairs and custom made. Initially the apse was empty, the sanctuary being a wholly independent structure with a shallow apse of its own in the form of a partition sufficiently high for a doorway in its northeast quadrant. The space between this partition and the apse wall proper formed a curved passageway between the pastophoria which were later extended eastwards creating an east court with an unidentified focus in the middle of its east wall [32.10]. Stone-paved outer corridors, c.6m across on the south and 4.8m across on the north, were articulated by deep pilasters supporting transverse arches [32.11]. The corridors ran the entire length of the aisles and against their outer walls benches filled the spaces between the pilasters

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[32.12-13]. Based on this evidence Megaw identified the corridors as *katechumenaia*. They were linked at their west ends by a narthex, 5.7m wide by 24.2m by [32.14] from which three doors communicated with the basilica, one with the diakonikon, one with the south-west court and one at the north end of the narthex led to the north atrium.

In the sixth-century the curved masonry screen closing the east end of the circumambulatory bema was demolished and the sanctuary relocated eastwards to fill the, hitherto, 'empty' apse. The new bema projected four bays into the nave but lacked projections into the aisles. The altar, which occupied an area between the first and second bays, was covered by a ciborium. The sanctuary and certainly the north aisle were paved in *opus sectile* [32.15] but the nave had a mosaic pavement and, on the evidence of glass tesserae and mother-of-pearl, the upper walls too were probably embellished with mosaic. What little survives of the solea suggests that it was a substantial affair and comparable to Ayia Trias [32.16]. The lower walls of the interior appear to have been revetted, often with plaques sawn from salvaged columns and framed with, possibly *spoliata*, champlévé panels. Four more triangular champlévé panels, c 4.60m-wide, decorated the ends of the aisles, the cutaway grounds of which would probably have been filled with black or coloured waxes (32.17). A possible *diakonikon* in the north-east corner of the complex had a central niche in its east wall, either side of which were the vestigial remains of two figures of Church Fathers and one of probably a pair of flanking, nimbed and wingless angels carrying sceptres for which a sixth-century date is suggested [32.18].

Probably laid out at the same time as the baptistery basilica and shortly after the construction of the episcopal basilica, the atrium consisted of a two-storey quadraportico supported on marble columns. In the upper gallery the marble bases were smaller and taller with slots on opposite sides to receive closure screens. There is no evidence that the shallow hexagonal *phiale* in the centre of the atrium was sheltered by a ciborium. Apart from the east portico the remainder of the area was stone-paved. Ceramic evidence suggests a date for the atrium of c.400 and seventh-century courseware indicates a *terminus ante quem*.

The ancillary buildings to the north and west of the atrium probably belonged to a two-storey *episkopeion*. The large mosaic-paved ground floor room on the north side of the atrium, with benches along its north and western side may have served as a waiting

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room. A staircase in its northwest corner accessed the upper levels [32.19]. The principle rooms, including an audience hall, courtroom and spacious galleries, which probably overflowed the narthex, may have been part of a sixth-century refurbishment. Some, at least, of the groundfloor rooms served for storage given the remains of a pithos set into the floor of one of them.

Much of the evidence for the buildings on the western edge of the complex was lost with the construction, in the sixth century, of the building with benches lining its north wall and identified as a *diakonikon* from the inscription in its pavement [32.20-1]. The adjoining court to the south with a central covered cistern was inherited from the Constantinian basilica.

Catalogue number	33	Location	Kourion	Map reference	34.44.33 N 32.59.42 E
Identification/ dedication	Extra-Mural Basilica	Date	Late 5th to mid 7th c	District	Limassol

This basilica occupies a site to the northwest of the city which rises steeply to the east. The excavations undertaken between 1971 and 1974 by the Department of Antiquities brought to light a small three-aisled, triapsidal basilica measuring 16.34m by 10.80m [33.1-2]. The columns of the arcade were mounted on high stylobates. The raised bema was enclosed by a low screen and a synthronon lined the central apse. The north aisle may have had a martyrial function given, firstly, a partition wall closing off its apsidiole from the remainder of the aisle, and secondly, an apse in its north wall containing a marble revetted tomb.

The aisles were stone paved and the décor of the nave pavement was divided into four panels. Recovered from the paving of the nave were two Roman slabs on one side of which were scenes of Poseidon, Amynone and the satyr and, on the other, the head of a water nymph - iconography suggesting an origin in the city's Nymphaeum. The walls too were part revetted in Proconnesian marble. Other *spolia* included two seats, probably from the stadium that lay 100m to the west, or the theatre that lay 1000m to the south, reused in the walls of the north aisle [33.3]. The spirally-fluted columns possibly from Troad may have defined the bema, given that plain marble columns were also recovered from the site together with Doric and Corinthian capitals [33.4].

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A corridor attached the north aisle separated the basilica from an apsidal ended annex which may have served as a treasury [33.5-6]. At the west end of the corridor aligned doorways allowed access from the annex into the north aisle of the basilica at a point exactly corresponding to a break in the stylobate at the west end of the north colonnade [33.7]. An annex attached to the south aisle ran uninterrupted for the entire length of the building. [33.8]

The basilica was preceded by a narthex and an atrium surrounded by colonnaded porticoes and paved throughout with limestone slabs. In the middle of the atrium there was a cistern that may have preceded the construction of the basilica. Its later conversion into a limekiln might explain the limited number of surviving marble columns. An entrance, from the city to the south, led into the south portico of the atrium [33.9] (cf. Kourion Limeniotissa and the north entrance to the Episcopal basilica). A corresponding entrance from the north flanked by ancillary rooms, led into atrium's north portico [33.10].

Catalogue number	34	Location	Kourion	Map reference	34.42.16 N 33.1.8 E
Identification/ dedication	Limeniotissa	Date	Late 4th, late 5th, early 6th c.	District	Limassol

Oriented 20° south of east, the basilica lies about 100m from the beach and was discovered in 1993. Publication is awaited.

Excavations exposed a building in two phases, a late-fourth, early-fifth century basilica and a late fifth or early-sixth-century three-aisled, tri-apsidal basilica, the apses of which were round on the interior and three-sided on the exterior [34.1-2]. The southern apsidiole, 2.70m across, was partitioned and may have contained a *mensa martyris* possibly related to the cult of St Hermogenes (c.f. the north aisle of the extra-mural basilica) [34.3]. This partition was revetted on its west face with Proconnesian marble and had a raised feature on its east side [34.4]. The aisles were separated from the nave by raised stylobates running the full length of the building each supporting six Proconnesian columns carrying Theodosian capitals, the easternmost four of which corresponded to the bema [34.5-6]. Two tall column bases mark the entrance to the bema the floor of which was paved in *opus sectile* which extended as far as the steps of the synthronon [34.7]. The floors of the nave and the aisles were carpeted with mosaics

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in a number of elaborate geometric designs including lozenges, rosettes, guilloches, cross-shaped ornaments, triangular and rectangular shapes and concentric circles. The best-preserved mosaics, belonging to the late-fifth or early-sixth century, were found in the south aisle and the eastern part of the north aisle. A late-fourth century, early-fifth century mosaic of intersecting rectangles arranged symmetrically was discovered under the entrance to the bema 0.03m below the later *opus sectile* floor. In the corridor attached to the south aisle a further floor dated to the late fifth century or the beginning of the sixth, consisted of large squares in red and black against an off-white ground. In a room outside the western part of the atrium (*diakonikon?*) an entire late-fourth century floor was preserved with a design of black squares on an off-white ground. During the excavations a large number of wall-tesserae were also recovered, including gold and mother-of-pearl, suggesting that the semi-dome of the apse and possibly the upper walls were also embellished with mosaic. Three portals gave access to the basilica from a mosaic-paved narthex [34.8] that doubled as the east peristyle of an atrium, the remaining floors of which were limestone flags [34.9]. A well, off-centre to the south of the atrium has been partly reconstructed. A possible entrance into the complex from the south led to the central bay of the atrium's south portico and there may have been a corresponding entrance from the north, similar to the entrances to the extra-mural basilica [34.10]. The porticoes of the atrium were supported on stone piers rather than columns with L-shaped supports at the corners. There may have been an ancillary space to the north of the north aisle given evidence for a doorway leading from the east end of the north portico. A doorway in the south wall of the south aisle led to an annex which may originally have been the full length of the aisle. There is little evidence for benches except for a small ancillary space to the south which appears to have had benches on its east, west and south sides.

Catalogue number	35	Location	Kourion	Map reference	34.40.32 N 32.53.15 E
Identification/ dedication	Nymphaeum	Date	Late 4th early 5th c.	District	Limassol

After the earthquake of c.365 the public baths of the city were abandoned and part of the structure was, according to Christou, converted into a Christian basilica of three aisles paved throughout with limestone flags, with a narthex at the northwest end and an apse to the southeast [35.1-3]. Adjoining the narthex further north-west, the cistern

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of the former Nymphaeum may have functioned as a baptistery [35.4-5] from about 370 to the completion of the Episcopal complex in the early fifth century.

Bibliography

- AJA* (1973) 431; (1975) 132; (1995) 344-5 fig 30
AR (1961) 45
ARDA (1957) 17; (1959) 18; (1973) 24; (1974) 28; (1975) 31-33; (1976) 36-38; (1977) 44-45; (1978) 39-40; (1979) 41; (1980) 38-9; (1985) 49-50; (1986) 52-4; (1987) 54-55; (1988) 59-60; (1989) 48-50 (1993) 63; (1995) 44; (1996) 51-52; (1997) 55-6; (1998) 66-7
BCH (1972) 1082; (1973) 687-88; (1974) 894; (1996) 1087-8; (1997), 917; (1998) 684; (1999) 620
Christou (1983) 50, 266-280
Dikigoropoulos (1940-48) 98
Hadjichristophin (2005) 405-411
Leonard (2005) 573
Megaw (1974) 64; (1976) 6; (1979) 358-365; (1993) 53-67; (1997) 343-352 ; (2007)
Megaw/du Plat Taylor (1981) 233, 235, 249-50
Michaelides (1993) 72 fig. 34; (1998) 213-4
Papageorgiou (1992) 2, 4
Soren (1985) 54
Whittingham (1982) 80-85
Young in Megaw (2007) 500
-

Catalogue number	36	Location	Lambousa (Lapithos/Lapta)	Map reference	35.20.50 N 33.17.52 E
Identification/dedication	Acheiropoietos	Date	4th-6th c.	District	Kyrenia

Located on the north coast, the Late Antique harbour city of Lapethos flourished until its destruction in the Arab invasion of c.649 and its final abandonment in 653-654 after a second attack. The dedication 'without hands' may derive from the 'Veronica' sent to Abgarus, King of Edessa. Alternatively, it may be the Turin 'Sudarium,' which, according to legend was taken from Cyprus by a princess of Savoy. Gunnis records yet another tale that the shroud in which Joseph of Aramathea wrapped the dead Christ was brought here from where it was removed to Turin. The basilica is now on a Turkish military base and, despite requests, could not be visited.

Three early basilicas have been located, one of which is under the present Middle Byzantine domed, cross-in-square church of the Acheiropoietos. The fourth-century

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basilica had three aisles terminating in three apses semi-circular inside and out, the foundations for which were largely cut from the bedrock [36.1-2]. Eastwards extensions of the north and south walls of the inner three aisles were linked by a third wall which effectively squared off the triapsidal east end, although to what height is unclear. The bema was paved in *opus sectile* and the main apse may have been lined with a synthronon although Soteriou made a case for opposed clergy benches. The apses were connected by narrow interapsidal passageways. The pavement of the north apse was raised to accommodate a low burial vault, reached by an exterior staircase. To the northeast of the sacristy a number of marble colonettes were discovered probably belonging to the chancel screen, of which one is in Limassol Castle. A chancel screen panel together four columns surmounted by Corinthian columns were reported in 1935 as having been reused in the later iconostasis [36.3]. It is probable that outer corridors were attached to the aisles, the eastern termination of which stopped short of the springing of the apses. Their straight east ends combined with the three apses would have given an eastern termination familiar from Agios Epiphanius and Soloi. The remains of a mosaic pavement were discovered in the southern outer aisle.

Several more capitals and columns from the early basilica were reused in the monastic buildings. A Proconnesian marble fragment from an ambo and now in Limassol Castle may also originated from Lambousa. Fragments of an *opus sectile* floor lie exposed close to the coast to the east of the site [36.4].

Bibliography

ABSA	(1946) 74-78
AR	(1953) 33
ARCA	(1915)7-12
Enlart	(1987 ed) 214
Goodwin	(1984) I. 918
Gunnis	(1936) 315-17
Hackett	(1901) 319
Hilton	(1935) 4
Jeffery	(1915-16) 111-134, (1918), 319-20
Megaw	(1955) 33; (1985) 201
Papacostas	(1995) Gazetteer 9 d.I.iii; (1999) II 2; III figs 1-2
Papageorghiou	(1964) 212-4; (1985) 299-324 at 304; (1986) 490-504 fig.3; (1993) 43-4, 72, fig. 9
RCAM	(1926) 10-11
RDAC	(1935) 4
Soteriou	(1935) 23, pls 25, 26, 145a
Stylianou/Harmanta	(1969) 19-29 pl 4
Van den Ven	(1953) 126

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Catalogue number	37	Location	Limassol (Λεμεσσο)	Map reference	34.43.51 N 33.0.7 E
Identification/dedication	Tychikos/ Nemesios?	Date	5th - 7th c	District	Limassol

During excavations in 1993 in the centre of Limassol, behind the Jami Kebir/Eski Jami mosque, the Department of Antiquities excavated the remains of a Middle Byzantine church built on the foundations of a Late Antique Basilica dating to between the fifth and the seventh centuries. Two apses remain of what would probably have been a triapsidal layout, each circular on the interior and polygonal on the exterior of which the southern apse preserves the earliest remains [37.1-2]. A fragmentary sarcophagus suggests that this apse may have served as a funerary chapel dedicated to Tychikos or Nemesios. On the interior of the northern and larger apse are the remains of a synthronon constructed in imitation of earlier examples. A coin of Constantine dating to 324/5 and pottery from the end of the seventh century were found in the early phase. There was a paved area to the east of the apses.

Bibliography

Procopiou (1997) 285-317

Catalogue number	38	Location	Livadia (Sazliköy)	Map reference	31.25.20 N 29.56.33 E
Identification/dedication	Panagia tis Kyris	Date	7th c.	District	Famagusta

Situated at the western end of the Karpas peninsula, the only cruciform church on the island is orientated 35° north of east [38.1-2]. The now-derelict building was erected on the site of an early Byzantine basilica which was itself erected over at least one cistern. Together with Kiti and Lythrankomi Panagia tis Kyris was one of the three former basilicas on the island with surviving Late Antique apse décor (see Chapter 4). Of the seventh-century apse mosaic of an orant Virgin against a gold ground only meagre fragments remain, notably a small section of border above the cornice in the centre of the apse. Given the fact that the feet of a figure have been discovered on a straight section of wall to its south it is possible that the composition extended across a large part of the basilica's east wall [38.3]. What remained of the mosaic in the early 1960s and recorded in *ARDA* for 1961, was destroyed in 1982 when looters attempted to detach it from the semi-dome.

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A sixth century date for the earlier church is suggested by the two Proconnesian chancel screen posts which now serve as impostes for the vault of the shallow north arm of the cruciform building [38.4]. There may be some indication of a synthronon in the masonry on the north side of the apse [38.5]. The small section of east wall south of the apse, where the feet of a figure were discovered, clearly shows that the south wall of the sanctuary was built against an earlier east wall [38.6]. The earlier building was probably a columnar basilica given a column, c.0.40m in diameter, to the south of the present church [38.7]. Two presses to the south and southeast of the site attest to a close relationship between the church and a community engaged in oleo- and viticulture [38.8].

Bibliography

Chotzakoglou	(2008) 122-3
Gunnis	(1936) 328
Jeffery	(1915/16) 122
Megaw	(1985) 195-8; (1985)195-98
Megaw	(1971) 261-263; (1976)
Megaw and Hawkins	(1976) 363-66 fig. 1. photos A and B
Megaw	(1985) 196-7, figs 14, 15
Michaelides	(1992) 122 no.71
Papacostas	(1999) II 53, III fig 171
Papageorghiou	(1966) 19 fig.10
Soteriou,	(1931) 484; (1935) pl. 34-35a
Stylianou	(1997) 52

Catalogue number	39	Location	Lysi (Akdoğan)	Map reference	33.41.0 N 35.6.30 E
Identification/ dedication	Panagia	Date	7th c	District	Famagusta

To the west of the village this three-aisled basilica was excavated in 1963. It cannot be dated much earlier than the seventh century when it was destroyed by fire [39.1]. Its pavement provides the only non-coastal example of *opus sectile*. Three tombs were discovered immediately under its pavement.

Bibliography:

AR	(1966) 42
ARDA	(1963) 15
BCH	(1964) 374-76
Michaelides	(1993) 75
Papageorghiou	(1963) 8-10; (1964) 157 fig.3

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Sodini

(1986) 236 and n. 47

Catalogue number	40	Location	Lythrankomi (Boltaşli)	Map reference	35.12.47 N 33.27.43 E
Identification/ dedication	<i>Panagia Kanakariá</i>	Date	Late 5th-6th c.	District	Famagusta

Inland at the western end of the Karpas Peninsula, Lythankomi can probably be identified with Late Antique *Erytha kome*, attested in the seventh-century *Life of St Spyridon*. Enlart noted that the Late Antique predecessor to the present church belonged to the Apendrika group and, according to Megaw and Hawkins it would probably have been built no later than the close of the fifth century [40.1].

There is no evidence that the columnar basilica was tri-apsidal before its remodelling as a pier basilica [40.2]. If Ayia Trias was the prototype for Lythrankomi it is likely that the basilica would have been preceded in the west by a narthex and an atrium. The only evidence for a narthex is a section of wall 3m to the north of the present north wall and the best evidence for an atrium is the suggestion by Megaw and Hawkins that three of the four stone shafts supporting the porch were too small to have come from the nave [40.3]. There is evidence for galleries at Ayias Trias but none are attested at Kanakariá.

The three aisled, timber-roofed basilica was orientated 10° north of east. Between 15 and 16m in length, the nave was 5.9m-wide and separated from the aisles by 5 stone columns, with, on the evidence of the north-east respond, four full columns embedded in the east and west walls receiving the arcades, the columns of which were almost certainly re-used from an earlier building. Such a layout would have given 6 intercolumniations of 2.50-2.66 and an overall proportion of between 1:2.54 and 1:2.71, close to the average for the Apendrika group. Five tall bases 0.73m square and 0.50-0.55 high, probably came from this first basilica [40.4]. Similarly the Theodosian capitals outside the west door fit with the diameter of the northeast respond [40.5]. The columns carried a clerestory, possibly with a turriform structure over the bema. There is no evidence of a synthronon; rather the arrangement seems to be of an earlier type with facing clergy benches either side of the altar (c.f. Lambousa) which confirmed Megaw and Hawkins in their late fifth-century dating before the advent of the

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synthronon in the sixth. At the end of the nineteenth century there was still said to be evidence for a masonry throne.

After the destruction of the first basilica in the mid-seventh century, the apse and sixth-century mosaic were incorporated into the later building as was also the case at Livadia and Kiti. Before its destruction in 1978 the apse mosaic depicted the Virgin on a lyre-backed throne with Jesus on her lap flanked by palms and Michael and Gabriel, all set against a gold ground [40.6]. On the intrados of the arch were thirteen medallions of the apostles, probably with a cross at the crown of the arch [40.7].

Bibliography

Chotzakoglou	(2008) 95-99
Cobham	(1908) 304
Enlart	(1987) 309
Enlart	(1926) 137
Dikigoropoulos	(1957) 50
Frankoudis	(1890) 411
Hogarth	(1889) 71-2
Jeffery	(1906) 485; (1918) 261-63
Megaw	(1974) 77
Megaw and Hawkins	(1977)
Michalopoulou-Charalampous	(1998) 216
Papacostas	(1999) II 50-51, III 163-7
Papageorghiou	(1964) 372-74; (1966) 221
Sakellariou	(1890) 106
Smirnov	(1897) 1-93
Soteriou	(1935) fig 31-33; pl 32-33
Stewart	(2008) 49-50; (2010) 174-177
Stylianou	(1985) 43-7 figs.12, 13,14
Van den Ven	(1953) 52, 56, 119 and 158

Catalogue number	41	Location	Marathovouno (Uluğişla)	Map reference	35.13.15 N 33.37.1 E
Identification/ dedication	No data	Date	5th-6th c	District	Famagusta

A three-aisled basilica with a single apse and preceded by a narthex was accidentally discovered immediately to the north of the village [41.1]. Probably built in the fifth or sixth century, it was remarkable in having arcades raised on piers, otherwise rare on the island at such an early date. The square-sectioned piers were built of rough masonry set in gypsum plaster to which base and other mouldings were added in the same material.

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Bibliography:

AR	(1966) 42
Megaw/Hawkins	(1977) 31, n.127
Papageorghiou	(1963) 84-101

Catalogue number	42	Location	Maroni (Μαρωνι)	Map reference	38.45.19 N 53.31.41 E
Identification/ dedication	Petrera	Date	2 phases to 7th c	District	Larnaca

In 1992/3 a short rescue mission discovered a late-antique church complex in two phases, together with a cistern and a public building, belonging to a settlement probably connected to the anchorage at *Maroni-Vrysoudia*. Coins found dated to 643-44 suggest the abandonment of the site sometime in the mid-seventh century.

Phase I consisted of a truncated three-aisled, triapsidal basilica 11.5 m. long and 12.50 m. wide [42.1]. The rounded central apse was approximately 3.6 m. across with walls 0.70 m. thick constructed with two courses of roughly-shaped limestone blocks and black river pebbles bonded with gypsum mortar and hydraulic cement and faced on both sides with a thick layer of plaster. Both the abutting north and south apses were smaller with a diameter of c.3.20m and a wall thickness of 0.50.m. The wall of the north apsidiole was constructed in an identical manner to the central apse, but the wall of the south apsidiole appears to have been less carefully assembled from limestone blocks set in gypsum mortar. This apse was not aligned with the central apse and the northern apsidiole, suggesting that what was originally a two-aisled church was converted into a tri-apsidal building by the addition of a south aisle. The north wall of the church was a simple continuation of the north wall of the apse and was traced for 8m where it turned through 90° to form the west wall.

A roughly constructed, plaster-faced, masonry bench inside the north wall was clearly a later construction, probably belonging to Phase 2 because it was built against the original plaster facing of the wall. The floor of the interior was paved with large gypsum flags.

At the end of the life of Phase 1 the apses were dismantled and what remained became the mid section of Phase 2, a three-aisled basilica with a single apse, semi-circular on the

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interior and four sided on the exterior, with aisles ending in straight east walls [42.2-3]. At the west end there was both a narthex and an exo-narthex built on to a buttress incorporated into the northwest corner of the building.

Bibliography

ARDA (1998) 46; (1998) 55-56
Manning *et al* (2002)

Catalogue number	43	Location	Mazōtos (Μαζωτοῦ)	Map reference	34.46.41 N 33.29.46 E
Identification/ dedication	<i>Petounta</i>	Date	Early 4th-6th	District	Larnaca

Situated on the edge of the cliff above the sea on the south coast, the nature of the building has yet to be established, but may have belonged to a larger ecclesiastical complex [43.1]. Construction was rubble, mostly river boulders, in poured gypsum plaster. A large transverse space dominated the complex, 2.8m across and of a length yet to be determined, but of which 8.8m had been excavated by November 2011 [43.2]. Leading off to the east were three rooms: the northernmost was a baptistery, the middle room had an east apse. The southernmost room was probably rectangular. The baptistery had a very small lobby, 1.33m wide by 0.70m deep, to the west followed by two steps down into the font and a further two out into a second lobby, 1.20m by 0.75m to the east [43.3]. The tank was 0.9m north/south and 0.50m east/west, made cruciform by two sets of stairs, 0.45m deep and 0.50m across. In favour of an early-fifth century date is the arris moulding which outlines the stairs and the base of the font, exactly the treatment at Ayia Trias. The fonts at *Petounta* and Trias were tanked in hydraulic plaster. At neither site was there evidence for revetting or mosaic although at *Petounta* one piece of marble provides the riser for the first step into the font from the west and another provides the font floor. The arrangement of the font is something of a puzzle; the stairs at *Petounta* are deepest in the east. The usual pattern would be steeper stairs in the west to dramatize descent following the rite of renunciation.

The middle chamber was a 3.4m square with an apse in its east wall, 1.2m deep and 1.3m across [43.4]. The proportions of the south chamber have yet to be determined. The complex appears to have been paved with marmara throughout.

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Bibliography

ARDA (2010) 84

Catalogue number	44	Location	Morphou (Güzelyurt)	Map reference	35.12.47 N 33.27.43 E
Identification/dedication	Agios Mamas	Date	5th-6th c.	District	Nicosia

Morphou lies in the western part of the Mesaoria on the south bank of the Serraches River, seven kilometres from the coast. Megaw's trail excavation in 1958 below the present 18th century building identified three churches of which only the first may have predated the Arab raids. It was a small, probably fifth- or sixth-century building on the evidence of the roof tiles and the small square bricks used in its construction. Under the nave of the present church, between the third and fifth columns from the east, a section of apse was discovered, 4.40m at the chord, and further south, between the third and fourth columns of the south arcade, a small section of wall or possibly a stylobate. A considerable amount of reused material was incorporated into the 18th century church possibly from this earlier building, including Mamas' shrine, a reused Roman sarcophagus built into the north wall, the Proconnesian columns framing the west portal [44.1], two more framing the Holy Door of the iconostasis [44.2] and the colonettes supporting the altar table.

Bibliography

AR (1959) 34
ARDA (1959) 19
Dikigoropoulos (1961), 185, pl.7
Megaw (1958) unpaginated
Papacostas (1999) II 56-7, 110; III fig 183-4
Papageorghiou (1993) 43; (2002) 66

Catalogue number	45	Location	Nicosia (Ledra)	Map reference	35.8.55 N 33.23.25 E
Identification/dedication	Panagia Hodegetria (Bedestan)	Date	Mid 5th - 6th c	District	Nicosia

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In 1937 Willis identified a tri-apsidal basilica, oriented 16° north of east the construction of which bore similarities with Aphendrika and Asomatos in the use of unglazed pottery sherds forced from behind to make the stones fit more tightly. He identified the dimensions of the apse as close to Aphendrika but, nevertheless, dated the Bedestan to the mid-fifth or sixth century [45.1]. On the basis of Karpasian comparanda, Willis estimated a basilica of about 20-25m in length probably of about six bays with inter-apsidal passages. However, the polygonal apse, which in the early period was predominantly a west and south coast phenomenon is absent from the Karpas. Given that the *opus sectile* floor of the Bedestan was identified by Megaw as sixth century it is possible that the apse too can be assigned to that date [45.2]. Two eastward projections from it and finds further east suggest a rectangular, axial annex. As a result of the recent renovation (the building was reopened in 2009) it appears that the three aisled basilica may have been preceded by a single-cell, apsidal-ended building.

Bibliography

Jeffery	(1906) 483
Megaw	(1951) 191-2
Michaelides	(1993) 75, fig.20
Papageorghiou	(1993) 48
Willis	(1986) 185-92

Catalogue number	46	Location	Nicosia (<i>Ledra</i>)	Map reference	35.7.34 N 33.23.41 E
Identification/dedication	St.George's Hill	Date	Unidentified	District	Nicosia

The site of the former building of the Association of Civil Servants (PA.SY.D.Y.) was allocated for the new House of Representatives. A rescue excavation was undertaken by Pilides for the Department of Antiquities at this extensive and complex site. A coin of the fourth century dates the earliest architectural remains and a coin of Constantine IV (668-685) confirms the occupation of the site beyond the Arab incursions. There appear to have been four phases of a church building orientated due east. Phase I consisted of a basilica with a single apse. A large cistern, 4.87m deep, by 4.45m x 7.07m, seems to have belonged with this church which, when excavated contained column drums as well as Late Antique roof tiles. The walls of the church were of unworked stones and the floor was laid with marmara flags. Phase II had three aisles and a tri-apsidal east end had a width of 15m (a modern chapel is set directly over its main apse) [46.1]. At 1.80m the

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walls were remarkably thick and were supported by equally thick rectangular sectioned buttresses, 1.5-2.00m [46.2]. A partially destroyed apse and part of the north wall of Phase III were found, possibly smaller than Phase II. The plan of Phase IV was almost intact.

Bibliography

ARDA (1997) 58-60; (2000) 56-61; (2006), 76-77
BCH (2000) 685-7 fig 42-3; (2001) 765 fig 45; (2005) 1678

Paphos (Πάφος): Introduction

Paphos had strong trade ties with Egypt since Hellenistic times which continued into the Roman and Late Antique periods, particularly with the diversion of the *annona* from Rome to Constantinople. From the late fourth century the city experienced economic growth which peaked in the first half of the sixth century, followed by a period of decline. The city's principal Late Antique basilicas, Chrysopolitissa and Limeniotissa, were extensively damaged in the Arab raid of 653.

Catalogue number	47	Location	Paphos (Πάφος)	Map reference	34.45.27 N 32.24.51 E
Identification/dedication	Chrysopolitissa	Date	End of 4th – 6th c	District	Paphos

Although now about 400m inland Chrysopolitissa would at the time of its construction have dominated the tri-partite all-weather harbour at Paphos.

Phase 1: Orientated 5° south of east, this enormous trapezoidal basilica was estimated by Christou to have been 48m long on its north side and 53m long on the south, although why the basilica should have been trapezoidal is unclear. The width of the basilica was 38m at the east end and less than 37m at the west end. It was raised on c.80 columns and covered an area of about 2130 sq.m [47.1-2]. It was excavated by Papageorghiou between 1971 and 1989 who dated the first of two phases to the end of the fourth century. His report remains unpublished and this important building has yet to be the subject of a major study.

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The basilica had seven aisles – a 9m-wide nave [47.3], 2.5m-wide inner aisles, 1.5m-wide-middle aisles, and 1.75m-wide outer aisles, making each block of aisles about 2m wider than the central aisle. The columns were principally of cippolino and granite [47.4-5], although there is also evidence of Proconnesian [47.6] and carian marble columns [47.7]. Corinthian capitals predominated [47.8]. The basilica was preceded by an atrium and a 4m-wide narthex, 0.40m lower than the basilica. In Phase I all seven aisles were enclosed in a box plan wholly without apsidal projections. A free-standing apse, circular on the interior and three-sided on the exterior, was set c.8m from the east wall and buttressed by two short sections of straight wall, aligned with the central aisle [47.9]. This apse formed the eastern conclusion of a sanctuary (or a nave) creating an-almost square court to the east [47.10] defined north and south by pairs of granite columns [47.11]. The floor of the court had a mosaic pavement with a geometric décor together with the chi-rho and an A and Ω in a roundel. Megaw suggested that the apse may have been constructed first and roofed while the remainder of the building was under construction. According to plans from the initial excavation, the central aisle was defined by intercolumnial closure screens. The mosaics of this aisle consisted of a line of square panels framing animals, plants and inscriptions, including a stag drinking water from a brook (the head is missing) and above it the well-known text from Psalm 41(42).

‘ΟΝ ΤΡΟΠΟΝ ΕΠΙΠΟΘΕΙ Η ΕΛΑΦΟΣ ΕΠΙ ΤΑΣ ΠΗΓΑΣ ΤΩΝ ΥΔΑΤΩΝ, ΟΥΤΩΣ ΕΠΙΠΟΘΕΙ Η ΨΥΧΗ ΜΟΥ ΠΡΟΣ ΣΕ (Ο ΘΕΟΣ).’

To the west of this panel is another with a sheep looking toward a vine, of which only the head survives. The inscription over the vine is from John 15:1,

‘ΕΓΩ ΕΙΜΙ Η ΑΜΠΕΛΟΣ Η ΑΛΗΘΙΝΗ.’

Under the vine’s leaves and to the left of the sheep there is another inscription ΕΥΧΗ ΗΣΥΧΙΟΥ suggesting that the mosaics were donated by one Esychios. The remaining motifs were largely geometric: intersecting circles with four leaves, larger and smaller squares, rosettes, circles and lozenges. For Megaw a late-fourth century date for the basilica is attested by the ‘bold character and larger tesserae of its original mosaic floors.’ He also pointed out that this must have been the Episcopal church of Paphos but, so far, no baptistery has been identified.

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Phase 2. In the sixth century the building was subject to a major refurbishment undertaken, according to an inscription at the west end of the north inner aisle, by an otherwise unidentified Bishop Sergius. The free-standing apse was demolished and the sanctuary was relocated to a new apse which, together with two apsidioles, broke through the former east wall. The central apse was furnished with a synthronon [47.12]. This apse was five sided externally and the apsidioles were three sided [47.13]. The floor of the east court was raised 0.40cm to become the new bema and embellished with a new mosaic pavement. *Parabemata* extended into the aisles. The floor of the nave was repaved in *opus sectile* and the aisles were either repaired or received new mosaics [47.14-17]. One of the most important changes was the reduction in the number of aisles from seven to five [47.18]. The columns of the nave survived intact, granite corresponding to the new sanctuary and cippolino corresponding to the nave and a single colonnade, an alternation of granite and cippolino, replacing the two colonnades dividing the aisles of Phase 1. The mosaic pavement at the east end of the southern inner aisle is probably a survival from the earlier phase [47.19]. With the Phase I colonnades removed two aisles per side remained, each of c.3m. The inner aisles corresponded to the apsidioles but the outer aisles ended in straight east walls [47.20]. It is not clear whether Phase 1 had galleries but they were a feature of Phase 2 when they extended over the narthex.

The narthex, mosaic-paved and at a lower level than the basilica, led to an *episkopeion* to the south [47.21]. To the west, and at a lower level still, lay a large atrium whose wedge-shaped east portico was also mosaic-paved, although the remaining porticoes were probably paved in stone [47.22]. The corners of the atrium were marked by T-shaped piers but the porticoes were supported on marble columns with ionic capitals [47.23]. The interior of the court had a stone kerb framing a mosaic floor. In the centre of the atrium there was a *phiale*, circular on the interior and polygonal on the exterior [47.24].

Catalogue number	48	Location	Paphos (Παφος)	Map reference	34.45.24 N 33.00.30 E
Identification/ dedication	<i>Limeniotissa</i>	Date	5th c	District	Paphos

Orientated due east, the basilica was located close to the harbour. It shares with the southwest basilica at Amathus the distinction of being the only other church so far

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discovered on the island with two narthexes but no atrium. Although identified by Philippou in 1937, systematic excavation did not begin until 1959 under Dikigoropoulos, with a further excavation undertaken by Papageorghiou in 1967.

The three-aisled basilica, 52m x 19 m, was preceded by a narthex [48.1-3] and possibly an *episkopeion* and was flanked, north and south, by long annexes. Like Kourion and Marathovouno it had three aisles but only one apse, semi-circular on the interior and six-sided on the exterior [48.4]. Marble columns on low stylobates separated the nave from the aisles [48.5]. The nave was paved in *opus sectile* and the aisles in mosaic with a predominantly geometric and floral décor [48.6]. An annex, also mosaic-paved, was attached to the north aisle. There was possibly an east court which accessed a subterranean chamber beneath the north aisle (cf Lambousa).

Catalogue number	49	Location	Paphos (Παφος)	Map reference	No data
Identification/ dedication	Shyrvallos	Date	5th/6th/7th c	District	Paphos

The three-aisled basilica discovered in 1962/3 at Shyrvallos, on the cliffs east of Paphos, was the subject of a rescue excavation having been badly damaged as a result of construction work. Attached to its north side was a long room terminating in what was possibly a small transept and an apse, semi-circular on the interior and three-sided on the exterior [49.1]. The room was divided into compartments with, at its east end, a cross-shaped depression in front of the apse. Pallas dates the building to the second half of the fifth century and Ristow to between the fifth and seventh centuries. A sixth-century mosaic formerly from the 'baptistry,' and now in Paphos Archaeological Museum, makes reference to an anonymous donor: 'Someone whose name only God knows, in fulfilment of a vow for the benefit of his family, laid this mosaic floor' [49.2-3].

Catalogue number	50	Location	Paphos (Παφος)	Map reference	34.45.58 N 32.24.30 E
Identification/ dedication	Toumballos (Garrison Basilica)	Date	4th c	District	Paphos

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The basilica was orientated due east and located to the west of the north gate of the city just inside its walls. Excavations were begun by the University of Catania in 1987 under Giudice and are ongoing. In 1988 the excavators uncovered the foundations of a basilical chapel built above a subterranean shrine near the Temple of Apollo Toumballos [50.1]. The remains consisted of a rectangular building raised over a cistern or tomb, the east wall of which, cut into the bedrock, contained a central niche (cf Ayios Tykhonas). To the east two apses succeeded one another on the same axis [50.2-3]. Among the artefacts uncovered were inscriptions on two ceramic shards with the names of St.Paul and St.Hilarion. The excavators speculated that the fourth-century building may have been a martyrium for Hilarion who reputedly drove demons from the pagan precincts of Paphos and, according to Jerome, preached near the ruins of a great temple at Paphos. A subterranean passage running north-south established the eastern limit of the building [50.4].

Bibliography

- AJA* (1968) 75 pl 24 fig 22; (1970) 395f; (1972) 316; (1973) 57; (1977) 532; (1980) 73; (1995) 347-8 fig 33
- AR* (1966) 43; (1968-9) 53-4; (1969-176) 69; (1980-81) 72
- ARDA* (1963) 15 fig.30; (1965) 11; (1967) 18; (1968) 17-18; (1969) 17; (1972) 13-14; (1973) 16; (1977) 46-7; (1978) 40-41; (1979) 42-3; (1980) 39;(1981) 40; (1982) 38-9; (1983) 40; (1984) 45-46; (1985) 48; (1986) 46-7; (1987) 48-9; (1988) 57-58; (1989) 54-5; (1990) 61-62; (1991) 59-61; (1998) 61-2; 1994 (1998) 54, 59-73; (2003) 42-3, 50-51; (2008) 65-66, 89-90
- Ballet* (1995) 179-202
- BCH* (1960) 292; (1964) 374, fig. 109; (1968) 351; (1969) 493-94, 504, 564-66; (1972) 1091; (1973) 624, 679-80; (1974) 895; (1975) 844; (1976) 899-900;(1977) 776-79 fig 114; (1978) 936; (1979) 722; (1980) 801; (1981) 1007; (1982) 737; (1983) 945; (1984) 859, 959-60; (1985) 957-59; (1986) 862; (1987) 691; (1988) 841; (1989) 837; (1990) 982; (1991) 825-27; (1992) 825 figs 76-77; (1993) 747 fig 47; (1994) 683-6 figs 60-4; (1995) 829 figs 44-5; (1996) 1091 fig 47; (1998) 692 figs 33 (incorrectly captioned at 691) and 35; (2003-4) 1690, fig. 78; (2005) 907-8
- Christou (2008) 116
- des Gagniers (1975) 224-5
- Giudice (1992) 91-103; (2004) 271-321
- Lund (1993) 11-25, 141-143 and figs 54-55
- Maier/Karageorghis (1984) 293, 301
- Megaw (1976) 11,17 figs 7,10,11,30; (1988) 14, 136-140 n.12, 146
- Michaelides (1974) 79; (1987b) 38 no 42 (1992) 33 no. 35-7 pl.XV; (1996) 139-152; (1998) 198-201
- Nicolaou (1963) 47-8, no 10, pl.VIII 6
- Pallas (1997) 274-275 fig.190
- Papacostas (1995) Gazetteer 12 d.II; (1999) II 24-5, 56, III figs 80-1, 182
- Papageorghiou (1964) 160-2 no 3, fig 6-7; (1969) 82-88 fig. 1; (1970) 4 fig 1; (1976) 7-10; (1982) 471; (1985a) 326-27 fig.2; (1985b) 318; (1985c) 305-7, 318,

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	326-7, fig2; (1986) 491-2, 501; (1993) 35 n.29; (1996a) 33-39, pls 6-12; (1996b) 6, 230
Raptou and Conroy	(2006) 317-343
Ristow	(1998) no.934, 306
Rupp	(1987) 38
Sørensen	(1983) 286; (1987) 272
Pelekanides and Atzaka	(1974) 146, no.139. pl 132, no.143, ll pl.134
Wharton	(1988) 66-67

Peyia/Pegeia (Πέγεια): Introduction

Situated on the west coast at Cape Drepanon, about fifteen kilometres north of Paphos, Peyia was founded in the Hellenistic period and grew to a settlement of some importance particularly in the sixth century. It had no fortification walls and seems to have been of a largely commercial character. Together with Kalavastos it is the largest Late Antique settlement excavated on the island, and shares with it a proliferation of basilicas. Where Kalavastos had embellishments in gypsum plaster, often in imitation of high status fittings, Peyia had Proconnesian fittings in abundance with marmara reserved for flooring, revetting benches and possibly for closure screens. Bakirtzis argued that the settlement's wealth derived from its role as a station in the transport of grain from Egypt to Constantinople between 330 and 618, but if so ships must have anchored off-shore because there is no evidence for a harbour. There were, however, anchorages at Kerati, Thalassines Selies and Lara, where sixth and seventh-century amphorae have been recovered. Bakirtzis further argued that Peyia flourished at the expense of the Akamas to the north and Paphos to the south which experienced economic decline from the middle of the sixth century. He links the decline of Peyia to the Persian capture of Alexandria in 618 and the consequent end of the *annona*. Michaelides cites the importance of the site as a stopover for pilgrims *en route* to the Holy Land. Unlike Kalavastos, abandonment of the site appears to have been peaceful. The last numismatic evidence is dated to Heraclius' reign (621-22).

Three basilicas were excavated by Megaw between 1952 and 1955, with further excavations between 1991 to 1998 by Bakirtzis and the Aristoteleian University of Thessalonika. Michaelides suggests the possibility of further basilicas in the vicinity. The basilicas are thought to have been built *de novo* under Justinian given the extensive use of Proconnesian marble. Megaw suggests that this suite of basilicas may reflect a

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reassertion of Aegean influence particularly in the quasi-transept of the baptistery basilica and the distinctive layout of the baptistery itself. He proposed the Central Basilica as Justinian and that the South Basilica 'was probably built in the late sixth century' with the North Basilica 'somewhat later.'

Catalogue number	51	Location	Peyia (Πέγεια)	Map reference	34.52.14 N 32.31.30 E
Identification/ dedication	Baptistery and Basilica	Date	Phases to the 6th c.	District	Paphos

A peristyle court in the centre of which was a font, together with a small basilica to the north of the court, was raised on a parterre west of the Central Basilica. [51.1-2]. A font in an open court is unique on the island [51.3]. It is quite different from early fifth-century processional baptisteries but closer to those excavated in the Aegean in which the font provides the focus of a spacious hall. At Peyia the font was circular with a single stairway of four steps on its east side [51-4]. The peristyle court was surrounded by a colonnade of Proconnesian columns on high bases supporting galleries. The porticoes were marmara-paved but the baptismal court had a mosaic pavement divided into a rectangular carpet to the east of the font and a larger rectangular carpet to the west. The whole floor was surrounded by a border of alternating lotuses [51.5] that also served to separate the eastern from the western carpet. The eastern carpet had trellis-work forming poised squares each with a ribbon weaving over and under its sides, together with alternating rows of crosses and stepped crosses. The larger part of the pavement had a décor of interlocking circles with a cross at the centre and stepped crosses in the interstices, the same as the décor framing the bema of the Central Basilica with which its pavement was presumably contemporary.

The three-aisled basilica to the north of the baptistery was orientated 15° north of east and may have been the earliest church on the site [51.6]. The aisles closed with inscribed apsidioles and the central apse, semi-circular on the interior, three-sided on the exterior, projected into the northern entrance to the whole complex and may therefore have been a later addition. The north apsidiole appears to have been separated by a partition from the north aisle [51.7]. The position of the closure screen posts is evident from the surviving sockets at the western edge of the bema [51.8]. Also surviving are the bases of three of the four octagonal shafts which once supported a ciborium. T-shaped piers at the east end of the arcades corresponded to pilasters

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against the outer walls and this arrangement has often been understood in terms of a non-projecting transept [51.19], a feature otherwise absent from the basilicas of Cyprus before Katalymmata. At the north end of the 'transept' a number of pieces of coloured marble were discovered which evidently formed part of a wall decoration, including flower petals, small discs and the figure of a saint. To the north of the basilica an annexe almost as long as the basilica itself was furnished with benches along its north and south walls. To the west of the basilica and its baptistery lay a two-storey *episkopeion* with rooms arranged around an interior courtyard.

Catalogue number	52	Location	Peyia (Πέγεια)	Map reference	34.52.14 N 32.31.30 E
Identification/ dedication	Central basilica	Date	6th c	District	Paphos

The Central Basilica was '[o]ne of the most opulent basilicas on the island'. Oriented 15° north of east, it measured 27.8m x 19m and consisted of a nave and two aisles, separated by colonnades of eight Proconnesian marble columns with Theodosian capitals and galleries over the aisles. [52.1-4]. The east end terminated in three lightly projecting apses, semi-circular on the interior and polygonal on the exterior with two faces to the apsidioles and three to the central apse. The bema, protected by marmara chancel screens, extended two bays into the nave and one bay into the aisles. A five-stepped synthronon with a projecting axial stairway lined the central apse [52.5-6]. The mosaic floor of the bema was decorated with marine life including birds, fishes, octopus, squid, crustaceans and a turtle in a floret trellis. The semi-circular panel at the foot of the synthronon carried an imbricated décor with a floral in-fill [52.7-8]

The floor of the nave, excavated in the 1950s, revealed extensive early repairs. Divided into four narrow carpets to the west and two deeper carpets to the east, its décor was entirely geometric with the exception of the fifth carpet from the west which was divided into five rows of eight panels each containing an animal standing against an orange tree [52.9]. A Proconnesian marble ambo of the bridge type, with an oval platform, was set axially across the two larger panels.

The atrium to the west was directly attached to the basilica without an intervening narthex [52.10]. The porticoes of the atrium were paved with marmara and the centre of the atrium was paved with mosaic with a border of intersecting circles forming

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spindles, then small black squares in white circles framing a panel with two pairs of affronted beasts, a wild boar and a bear and a lion and an ox [52.11]. Along the north side of the atrium and the basilica were a series of annexes the most easterly of which, probably treasury, also terminated in a three-sided apse.

Catalogue number	53	Location	Peyia (Πέγεια)	Map reference	34.54.13 N 32.19.36 E
Identification/ dedication	North Basilica	Date	Mid to end of 6th c or early 7th c	District	Paphos

A sixth-century bath complex, probably part of a large villa, lay to the north of the Central Basilica and about 50m northeast of this lie the remains of the North Basilica. The North and the South basilicas followed broadly the same layout and may have been intended as complementary structures, although at 14.6m by 11.5m the North Basilica was the smaller of the two. It was oriented 20° north of east and consisted of three aisles terminating in apses, semi-circular on the interior and three-sided on the exterior [53.1-2]. The central apse was lined with a synthronon, probably of three tiers [53.3].

Nave and aisles were divided on each side by four Proconnesian columns set on raised stylobates, except at the west end where the floor was continuous on the north and marked by a low threshold on the south. The stylobates were capped and revetted in marmara, the covering used for all the floors. Despite the similarities between the North and South basilicas there seems to have been an intention to distinguish each of the three Peyia basilicas by their capitals, Corinthian in the Central Basilica, Ionic in the South Basilica, while in the North Basilica the capitals were formed from an inverted, truncated pyramid framed on all faces, with crosses toward the nave and aisles and discs toward the arcades [53.4]. Unlike the plethora of benches in the South basilica, the interior of the North Basilica had a single bench against the south wall of the south aisle.

The bema extended two bays into the nave and occupied one bay of the south aisle. In the north aisle the floor was continuous except for a platform roughly corresponding to the column of the first bay from the east. Two doorways in the north aisle led to a narrow marmara-paved corridor extending beyond the length of the north aisle at its west end. A doorway to the east of the platform was all-but aligned with a doorway on the north side of the corridor led to a rectangular room, also marmara-paved which,

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given its location, may have served as a treasury [53.5]. Amongst the other ancillary rooms to the north of the basilica Bakirtzis identified a sixth-century, two-storey *apanteterion* or guesthouse, a cistern, an olive-press and a 'storehouse for keeping the marble altar-tables from Constantinople before their sale in Paphos.'

The principle difference from the South Basilica is the lack of any evidence for an atrium. Instead the basilica was preceded by a narthex and porch divided by a tribelon supported on two Proconnesian marble columns [53.6]. The inner narthex was lined with benches and paved with marmara and the porch was stone paved.

Catalogue number	54	Location	Peγia (Πέγεια)	Map reference	34.54.13 N 32.19.36 E
Identification/dedication	South Basilica	Date	Middle to end of 6th c	District	Paphos

The basilica, 200m to the south of the Central Basilica, was orientated 45° north of east [54.1]. Measuring 14m by 17m, the basilica had three aisles and three apses, all semi-circular on the interior and three-sided on the exterior [54.2]. The central apse was lined with three-tiered synthronon [54.3]. A large rectangular annex to the north was accessed from two doorways, one from the north aisle and one from the northern *parabemata*. Marmara, with which the whole complex was paved, was used as revetment for the benches that lined the interior north and south walls. The nave arcades were supported on five Proconnesian columns with ionic-impost type capitals supporting galleries. [54.4-5]. The stylobates may have stopped one bay short of the west end creating a transverse aisle similar to Kalavastos-*Sirmata*. The bema extended almost two bays into the nave and *parabemata* filled one bay in the south aisle and rather more than one bay in the north aisle.

The basilica was preceded by a narthex and an atrium. The narthex had benches along its east wall. It also shared another feature with *Sirmata*. At the south end of the narthex a tomb was cut into the floor in the early-seventh century [54.6]. It was possibly occupied by the remains of a benefactress and her children, given the discovery there of part of a gold necklace, ear-rings, a cross pendant and a child's ring as well as copper coins, the latest of which was Heraclian.

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Bibliography

ARDA	(1953) 15; (1954) 17; (1956) 15
AR	(1955) 45
Asemakopoulou-Atzaka	(1980) 106, 147, pl.53γ, δ
Bakirtzis	(1995) 250
Giangrande	(1987) 191-2
Megaw	(1950) 15; (1954) 175; (1960) 348, pls xxxix-xl; (1974) 70-1 fig E 71-2 fig.19; (1976) 15f. figs 19,20,21,26, 34, 37; (1994), fig. E; (1997), 350-351
Michaelides	(1987b) 48-50 fig. 56-60; (1993) 73; (2001) 53, 59
Morris and Peatfield	(1987) 200-202
Papageorghiou	(1985) 314-316; (1986) fig 7
Pelekanides and Atzaka	(1974) 150ff no.147 pl 139

Catalogue number	55	Location	Polis (Πολις)	Map reference	34.48.47N 33.6.28E
Identification/dedication	Arsinoe EGO	Date	6th c	District	Paphos

The basilica, 32m by 18m, was discovered in 2000 on a bluff about 100m north of a second basilica at Polis-Chrysochous. This three-aisled basilica had a single polygonal apse [55.1-3]. The apse was probably decorated with mosaic, indeed the surviving material - Proconnesian marble columns [55.4], bases [55.5] and Theodosian capitals [55.6], together with sculpture, including champlevé panels, and fine limestone *transennae* – suggests a building of some opulence. Like neighbouring Chrysochous, Arsinoe was the site of a considerable number of burials, some below floor level where a small piece of fourth-century floor mosaic was also discovered - although whether belonging in an ecclesiastical context is unclear. A small and probably funerary apse was built into the north wall [55.6]. Floors were a combination of *opus sectile* and mosaic.

Catalogue number	56	Location	Polis (Πολις)	Map reference	34.48.49N 33.5.23E
Identification/dedication	Chrysochous (EF2)	Date	Mid to late 6th c.	District	Paphos

Chrysochous and Arsinoë are located within 200m of each other on the road to the sea (Verginas). Ćurčić described the building as ‘utterly destroyed, its rising walls completely gone, its foundations robbed of some of their stone, its marble decoration stripped, and its architectural sculpture plundered.’ The basilica was discovered in the 1920s but the

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first systematic excavations of Ancient Marion were begun in 1984 by the American Archaeological Expedition of Princeton under Childs, and are on-going. An inscription found at Chrysochous, now in the Cyprus Museum, records the fifth-century reconstruction of a basilica by Archbishop Sabinus and Bishop Photinos, but it is not clear Chrysochous was the basilica referred to. Located just to the northeast of a major crossroads, this three-aisled and tri-apsidal basilica measured 23m by 12.5m [56.1-2]. The rubble wallwork included large quantities of river boulder. The décor was probably sumptuous. The nave was divided from the aisles by arcades supported on Proconnesian columns with Theodosian capitals. Fragments of a marble closure screen may belong to the bema. Coloured stone and glass tesserae attest to the richness of its interior, although fragments of painted plaster suggest that the nave may have been treated differently. The floors were paved in *opus sectile*. Tombs were built against the south wall of the south aisle [56.3]. A narthex, excavated in 1986, was originally open and supported by two pillars on its west side [56.4]. It may have been contemporary with a portico added to the south of the basilica which looked out on a walled court, traces of which have been identified.

Bibliography

- Adavasio (1975) 349-51
ARDA (1985) 52; (1986) 43; (1987) 57-8; (1989) 55-6; (1990) 62-3; (1991) 61-62; (1992) 59-60; 1994 (1998) 73; 1995 (2003) 47; 2000 (2007) 53-5
BCH 113 (1989) 837; (1990) 982-83; (1991) 789-833 at 827-9; 116 (1992) 819; 119 (1995) 800-838 at 829-832
Caraher/Papalexandrou (2011)
Childs (1988) 121-130 pls XXXVIII-XL
Ćurčić (1986) 87-8
Najberg/Nicklies/Papalexandrou (2002) 139-154

Catalogue number	57	Location	Pyla (Πύλα)	Map reference	38.52.60 N 33.42.99 E
Identification/dedication	Koutsopetria	Date	Not identified	District	Larnaca

This large coastal settlement prospered in the fifth century, declined in the sixth and prospered again in the early seventh. Trial excavations began at the Early Christian site in 1993 and 1997 revealing parts of a large building which the excavator, Hadjicosti

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believed to be a Christian basilica. Large dressed rectangular sandstone blocks, smaller limestone boulders and gypsum were used in the construction. The walls were also plastered with gypsum, and there was evidence for marble revetment covering the lower walls of the interior. The presence of iron nails suggests the building would have been timber-roofed. By 1997 three rooms had been excavated including an apse. Large pieces of cement flooring found in the destruction layer suggest that the building was, in part, two-storied. There was also evidence for *opus sectile* paving. Architectural fragments included moulded gypsum with incised and brightly painted decoration and four gypsum plaster window lattices. Other décor included incised imagery including animals and birds on ships and crosses, as well as floral designs, quatrefoils and imbrication. Among the small finds were coins from the fifth to the middle of the seventh centuries. In 2006 it was suggested there may have been a second church on the site.

Bibliography

ARDA (1998) 70-72; (2006) 68-9; (2007) 78-9
Pettegrew/Caraher/Moore (2004) Conference paper
Pettegrew/Caraher/Moore/Noller
(2005) 245-266
Pettegrew/Caraher/Moore (2006) Conference paper

Catalogue number	58	Location	Rizokarparso (Dipkapaz)	Map reference	No data
Identification/dedication	No data	Date	5th-8th c.	District	Famagusta

Possible basilica identified by Mersin University dated to between the fifth and the eighth centuries

Bibliography

Kibris (4/9/01)

Salamis: introduction

The Late Antique harbour city of Salamis lay 8km north of Famagusta on the east coast of the island. One of the most affluent cities in the east, Salamis was the island's capitol

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and the seat of its Metropolitan. After 332 the emperor Constantius II renamed Salamis 'Constantia' rebuilding it as a Christian city. The harbour, the Porto Constanza, was important in the integration of Salamis in the pilgrimage networks of the eastern Mediterranean.

A mountain pass across the Pentadaktylos Mountains linked Salamis via Kythraia to the north coast. The famous springs of Kythraia supplied Salamis via an aqueduct a small section of which remains on the outskirts of the village of Agios Sergios, to the west of the city. A group of arches completed under Herculius are recorded by inscription.

The remains of three basilicas survive, Agios Epiphanius and Campanopetra lay in the southern suburb of the city and Agios Varnavas lay a short distance to the west. In addition, a sixth-century chapel built over two Roman cisterns lay between Agios Epiphanius and Campanopetra. Agios Epiphanius was burnt down in the first Arab raids and its east court was turned into a multi-domed church which overlooked the ruins, the former walls of which now constituted its atrium. New Byzantine fortifications enclosed Agios Epiphanius but Campanopetra remained extra mural.

Catalogue number	59	Location	Salamis	Map reference	351248N 332839E
Identification/ dedication	Agios Epiphanius	Date	Phase 1 Late 4th - early 5th Phase 2 6th - early 7th c.	District	Famagusta

Agios Epiphanius was the largest and the most influential building on the island. While its original dedication is uncertain, by the early fifth century the basilica was dedicated to Epiphanius. An account of its construction is given in the *Vita Epiphanii*:

God instructed Epiphanius to build a larger church; the construction of the church started with much animosity from the pagan administration of the city; one of Epiphanius' critics Faustina was mortally wounded when the construction workers accidentally dropped an ashlar block on his head; immediately Epiphanius fell on Faustinus and healed him, resulting in his conversion; after Epiphanius dies, his disciple Drakon asked permission from the Emperor to bury Epiphanius in this same church. Arcadius allowed Epiphanius' relics to be buried in the church where he healed Faustinus, in the south aisle apse.

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If the basilica is dated the last years of the fourth century and the beginning of the fifth there may well have been an earlier church if not on the site, at least in the vicinity, given that Epiphanius had been bishop of Salamis since 367. Rapp and Stewart, however, have raised doubts about an earlier church on the present site.

The complex falls into three principal phases (1) the great seven-aisled Episcopal basilica of the late fourth/early fifth century, (2) its sixth-century remodelling, and (3) the conversion of the east court into a timber-roofed and then a domed basilica on piers in the seventh century. The description of the site is confined to the first two phases.

The Basilica

Agios Epiphanius may not have been completed by the death of Epiphanius in 403. The site was excavated in 1924-5 by Jeffery and by the Department of Antiquities under Dikigoropoulos between 1954 and 1958. Orientated 30° north of east, the complex consisted of the basilica preceded by an atrium almost as large as the basilica itself, together with an eastern court at the far end of which was a baptistery [59.1-2]. It was limited to the east by a north-south *cardo* and in the west by the *cardo maximus* joining the agora and the theatre.

Phase 1

The basilica was 58m by 42m and constructed in well-finished ashlar masonry, laid alternately header and stretcher [59.3]. Its interior consisted of seven aisles: a nave with twin aisles and a narrow outer aisle [59.4]. The nave terminated in a central apse which sprang not from the east wall but some way inside it and from which it, therefore, projected only modestly [59.5]. The inner aisles terminated in inscribed apsidioles [59.6], the outer aisles in shallow rectangular recesses and the narrow outermost aisles accessed the ancillary spaces to the east of the basilica [59.7-8]. On the north a sacristy abutted the east end of the twin aisles [59.9] and on the south the east court corresponded to the southern aisles [59.10]. Passageways, c.0.80m wide, passed through the walls of the apse and apsidioles allowing access across the entire east end of the building [59.11-12].

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Outside the aisles but attached to them two pairs of corridors extended along the full length of the basilica. The northern inner corridor had two sets of stairs that may have accessed galleries. As there were no corresponding staircases in the south corridor a gallery over the southern aisles may have been access via a transverse gallery perhaps over the narthex. The outer corridors were articulated by pilasters similar to the outer corridors at Kourion identified by Megaw as *katechumenaia*.

The nave had thirteen columns assembled from spoliated drums, on bases 1.30m square set on a stylobate 1.40m across. The hammered surfaces of the columns suggest they would have been rendered or, as Michaelides suggests, decorated with marble *crustae*, although an embellishment of this quality may have been confined to the sanctuary [59.13:2.77]. The capitals appear to have been purpose made [59.14]. A surviving capital fragment lacks abacus and necking but is nevertheless 110cm high. Fourteen columns separated the two inner aisles and fourteen piers with attached shafts toward the nave separated the middle aisles from the narrow outer aisles [59.15-16]. These outer aisles were also defined by screens, probably of wood, fixed between the piers [59.17], except at the east and west ends which were open, providing access across the building, allowing a complete circuit of the interior [59.18]. For the eastern transverse 'aisle' to function, a circumambulatory bema would have been located to the west of it (cf Soloi B and Kourion). A circuit not 'interrupted' by a bema would have allowed pilgrims access to the marble-lined tomb, probably of Epiphanius located, not the apse identified by the *Vita* but in the southern rectangular recess [59.19]. According to the *Vita* the immediate vicinity of the tomb was decorated with gold and coloured mosaics with scenes from the life of the saint

At the west end, a narthex extended beyond the width of the basilica and terminated in an exedra to the south, which has been excavated, and another is presumed to the north. The atrium has been identified but not excavated. At the east end of the basilica the probably unroofed courtyard may have had a fountain as its focus. It is possible that this court had a mosaic pavement because when it was converted into a church after the Arab raids, the synthronon of the new church was laid on an existing mosaic floor. Immediately to the east of the court a mosaic-paved corridor probably led to an entrance from the north-south *cardo*. To the south of the corridor lay an apsidal-ended chapel, entered from the west, and paved with four large slabs of marble framed in *opus*

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sectile. [59.20-1] Karageorghis suggests this chapel was intended for catechumens. To the north of the corridor lay the baptistery described in Chapter 3.

Phase 2: During the course of the sixth century the basilica was subject to a major renovation. The columns separating the twin aisles were removed making one large aisle flanking either side of the nave [59.22]. The bema was relocated eastwards to occupy the hitherto empty apse. The apse was lined with a synthronon but is not clear whether there was a *kyklion* or whether the synthronon rendered the transverse passages unserviceable. The sanctuary, which penetrated three bays into the nave, did not occupy its full width but stopped short of the stylobates by about c. 0.80m. One bay further west lay what was probably an extension of the bema which occupied the whole width of the nave. According to Stewart's reconstruction the renovations may have occasioned a radical reduction in the number of western doorways to a single, central portal.

Catalogue number	60	Location	Salamis	Map reference	35.12.48 N 33.28.39 E
Identification/ dedication	Agios Varnavas	Date	Late 5th c	District	Famagusta

Agios Varnavas is lies less than 2km to the west of Salamis. The present double cross-in-square basilica belongs to the late-eighth or early-ninth century, and rests on the foundations of a late fifth-century, timber-roofed columnar basilica possibly destroyed in the aftermath of the Arab raid on Salamis in 649. Orientated 10° north of east and covering an area of about 800 sq.m, the basilica was probably tri-apsidal but only the much-rebuilt central apse and the southern apsidiole remain, although a north apsidiole is assumed. This may be the building identified in the sixth-century *Sancti Barnabae Laudatio*, erected at the expense of Emperor Zeno, (474-91) following the discovery of Barnabas' tomb by Archbishop Anthemius in 477.

The east end of the Late Antique basilica was discovered by Mogabgab in 1934. Its length may be indicated by the remains of 5th century wallwork in the west wall of the church which now occupies the site [60.1-2]. The nave of the Late Antique basilica was 8.15m wide, the north aisle was 3.82m and the south 3.45m and the stylobate supporting Proconnesian columns was 0.70m wide [60.3]. The main apse was 3.5m deep and the sanctuary extended to the full width of the nave. A five-stepped synthronon,

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without axial projection, was possibly a sixth-century addition [60.4]. The bema floor was paved with marble plaques framed in *opus sectile* similar to the apsidal-ended room attached to the east court at Agios Epiphanius [60.5]. It is not clear whether the sanctuary extended into aisles. The eastern respond of the south-side colonnade is not an attached shaft rather the east wall has been gouged out to receive a full, certainly spoliated column with the intention of giving it the appearance of a half shaft [60.6]. The notched base on the south stylobate and embedded in the buttress of the later church is possibly associated with a closure screen [60.7]. The spoliated capitals set into the interior walls of the present church may have come from the Late Antique basilica [60.8].

Until Megaw (2001) the *mensa martyris* filling the south apsidiole had been identified with the relics of Barnabas and described in the *Laudatio* as having been embellished with silver ornaments and marble columns [60.9]. What remains *in situ* is a single stone, 116 cm deep and 276 cm across, pierced by a funnel 14cm across. Beneath this cap stone was a recess 148cm across, 77cm deep and 45 cm high.

Catalogue number	61	Location	Salamis	Map reference	35.12.48 N 33.28.39 E
Identification/ dedication	Campanopetra	Date	5th-6th c	District	Famagusta

On the south-eastern outskirts of Salamis, barely 400m to the east of Agios Epiphanius, lay a second enormous basilica. Campanopetra was the alternative site proposed by Megaw as the martyrion of Barnabas, in which case it would have been funded by Zeno, although it may not have been completed until Anastasius 1. Agios Epiphanius, Agios Varnavas and Campanopetra all testify to a martyrial function and it is possible that, in a Salamis integrated into the pilgrimage networks of the eastern Mediterranean, all three served as stations in a penitential circuit.

The Atria

The site was excavated by Roux between 1964 and 1974. The complex, orientated 15° north of east, was over 152m from east to west with a north-south dimension of 28m in the east and 38m in the west [61.1-2]. The basilica was situated between three atria. – two attached to the west and one to the east. The outer western atrium, 36m by 37.8m,

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was porticoed except to the west where a wall separated it from the adjoining *cardo* [61.3]. The inner atrium, 47m long by 37.8m wide, may predate the basilica [61.4]. When the basilica was constructed an octagonal *phiale* was added to this inner atrium [61.5]; around it were 60 or more cells on two levels, possibly for pilgrims, monks or both.

The eastern atrium, 28.35m by 27.85, was linked to the western inner atrium by two 3m-wide corridors flanking the basilica allowing a full circuit of the building. A large pyramid-roofed ciborium set against the east portico provided the principal focus which Megaw suggested may have constituted a display of relics comparable to the *proskynesis* of Golgotha. The site's excavator, however, proposed the alternative hypothesis that the ciborium housed a relic of the True Cross. Toward the end of the fifth century or the beginning of the sixth the circuit was disrupted when the south corridor was blocked by the construction of an apse. The eastern half of this now-truncated corridor was converted into an *opus-sectile* paved cemetery chapel [61.6], leaving the northern corridor as the sole means of access between the eastern and western atria. A monumental stairway (c.f. Gerash) connected the eastern atrium to the harbour [61.7]. The stairway overflowed a cistern and a bathhouse noted for its fine *opus sectile* pavement [61.8].

The Basilica

A narthex ending in exedra north and south preceded the three-aisled, triapsidal basilica [61.9]. The basilica was 51.6m long and 28.2m wide. Its central apse was semi-circular inside and out and lined with a synthronon without projecting axial stairs [61.10]. The *opus sectile* paved apsidioles were horseshoe-shaped [61.11]. A half barrel-vaulted *kyklion* ran beneath the upper level of the synthronon [61.12] in the inner wall of which were three recesses each c. 90cm high, 90 cm wide and 65cm deep which probably housed liturgical vessels [61.13], one of which was directly beneath the throne, identified against the outer wall of the *kyklion* by an inscribed cross [61.14].

The bema extended two-and-a-half bays into the nave and was set inside the arcades by c.1m. A short solea extended westwards from the bema aligned, a few metres further west, with an ambo of the bridge type. The east ends of the aisles were separated from the remainder of the aisles by screens at the first bay.

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The nave arcades were raised on eleven Proconnesian columns set on roughly-cut bases, the profiles of which were characterised by two flattish torus mouldings divided by a v-shaped groove [61.15]. The columns were crowned by Theodosian capitals enriched with gold leaf on red primer which Roux suggests would have been sculpted by a workshop brought from Constantinople. The responds were sawn half-columns set on full bases sometimes crudely cut back to fit their setting [61.16]. The column bases were set directly on the pavement rather than raised on a stylobate and the arcades supported galleries over the aisles. The nave was paved in white, yellow and black *opus sectile* including fragments from a dedication slab with the name *Ioannis*. The aisles and the intercolumniations too were paved with large yellow marble slabs with the exception of a panel of *opus sectile* corresponding to the two bays at the west end of the north aisle.

At the east end of the north aisle there was a second *loca sancta*; a lidless sarcophagus (although there are tenons at each end to receive a lid) - 70cm deep by 130cm wide – with three holes at its base, one on the south face in two to the west, probably for drawing off oil after contact with the relic [61.17]. The martyrial context of this apsidiole is confirmed by comparing the revetment in the north and south apsidioles – the north apsidiole was revetted in Breccia corallina in which reds and pinks predominated, while and the south apsidiole was revetted in Proconnesian marble [61.18-19].

Attached to the north side of the north corridor was an apsidal-ended chamber, identified by Roux as a baptistery [61.20]. It is difficult to accept this identification given the proximity of Agios Epiphanius, unless Campanopetra took over that role following the torching of the Episcopal basilica in 649. There are paired recesses in each of the north, south and west walls. The western entrance was rebated for a door which led to a lobby similarly rebated [61.21]. The doorway from the lobby was almost directly opposite a doorway into the eastern enclosure of the north aisle from where the bema could be accessed through an opening in the closure screen.

There is little evidence that Campanopetra was damaged in the first Arab raids (save for a few Arab slogans), while Agios Epiphanius only a short distance away was destroyed – suggesting that destruction may have been exemplary. In the twelfth century the walls

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were still standing although the roof was gone. Roux suggests a final catastrophic collapse in the thirteenth century.

Catalogue number	62	Location	Salamis	Map reference	35.10.42 N 33.53.65 E
Identification/ dedication	Forum Basilica	Date	5th or early 6th c.	District	Famagusta

The conversion of the temple of Zeus proposed by Yon is doubted by Rautman who accepts a three-aisled, tri-apsidal basilica, 27m by 17m, constructed in the east portico of the forum of which there are few extant remains apart from evidence for an *opus sectile* paving. Six columns divided the nave from the aisles and the basilica was preceded by a narthex [62.1-2].

Catalogue number	63	Location	Salamis	Map reference	35.10.56 N 33.54.16 E
Identification/ dedication	Hagiasma of Nicodemus	Date	6th c	District	Famagusta

A sixth-century chapel was built over two round, first-century Roman cisterns which lie between but to the north of a road leading from Agios Epiphanius to the shore [63.1]. The *Hagiasma* (=Holy Water) was excavated in 1933. Each c.3m-diameter cistern was linked by a two-tier passage, about 1m wide, extending eastwards beyond the second cistern to a vertical shaft [63.2]. A second vertical shaft dropped directly into the first cistern. The walls were rendered with gypsum plaster. A religious function is attested by crosses, six inscriptions and a 1m by 4m tempera panel of the late fifth or sixth-century with large green and blue plants with broad leaves painted in the first cistern. Near the top border on each side a duck sits on a nest in the form of a lotus. On the right there appears to be a fish and flamingo, and closer to the centre, what are probably eels. Above there is a medallion of a bearded Christ Pantocrator.

Inscriptions surrounding the arch include 'Help, O Constantine, thou and thy sign,' and Elisha's saying as he turns the water of the spring at Jericho from bitter to sweet: 'Thus saith the Lord, I have healed these waters' (2 Kings 2, 19-22). Two further inscriptions read 'The voice of the Lord upon the waters...the Lord is upon many waters (Psalm 29 (28) 3). The inscriptions were probably associated with the orthodox Benediction of the Waters on the eve of Epiphany, celebrating the Jordan event. If baptism did not take

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place in the cisterns water could have been drawn up into the chapel above. A second inscription links the major Salamanic saints; ‘Barnabas the apostle is our foundation. Epiphanius our great governor,’ (ΒΑΡΑΒΑΣ Ο ΑΠΟΣΤΟΛΟΣ ΣΤΙΡΗΓΜΑ ΗΜΟΝ ΕΠΙΦΑΝΙΟΣ Ο ΜΕΓΑΣ ΕΠΑΡΧΟΣ ΗΜΟΝ). If Campanopetra was the Barnabas martyrrium the inscription could be a reference to the major *loca sancta* a short distance to the east and the west of the Hagiasma. A further inscription reads ‘God...protect us...Jesus, remember us...God is declared’, and below the panel, ‘Christ, O God, O Saviour, shelter and preserve thy servant Nicodemus...,’ - presumably the patron of the painted scheme.

Bibliography

- AJA (1968) 373-4; (1970) 394; (1972) 313
AR (1957) 49-50; (1959) 32
ARDA (1957) 16; (1959) 17; (1966) 11; (1968) 15-16; (1970) 14; (1973) 24; (1975) 27
Bardswell/Sotirou (1939) 443-445
Callot (1985) 357
Cobham (1908) 165, 256-57
de Boor (1983-85), 343-44
Delvoye (1972) 17, (1980) 313-17
Dikigoropoulos (1961) 182-89
du Plat Taylor (1933) 97-108
Enlart (1926) 143
Gunnis (1936) 224, 419-20; 419-424
Hayes (1980) 375-388
Jeffery (1918) 230-234, 238-39; (1928) 344-349
Karageorghis (1960) 288, 290
Krautheimer (1986) 511 n.65
Megaw (1957) 29-30; (1974) 61-64, 68, 73; 78 n.85; (1986) 517 fig. 12; (2006) 394-404; (2007) 157
Metcalf (2009) 311-3, 369
Michaelides (1992) 1; (1993) 74-5 pl. 12
Pallas (1984) 503-504
Papacostas (1995) 36-38 Gazetteer 13; (1999) II 19-20, 27-8, 89; III fig 69-72, 90
Papageorghiou (1965) 226-227 ; (1985) 301-304; (1986) 498, fig 1
Pliny/Rackham (1942) 319
Pouilloux (1969) 47 fig. 3
Rapp (1991) 86-7, 149; (2005) 18
Rautman, (2002) www.stoa.org/hopper
Rosser (1999) 723
Roux (1969) 50 fig. 3; (1998); (1993) 198-204
Sacopoulo (1962) 62-87
Sodini (2000) 767-778
Soteriou (1935) 11 fig.5 pl.8-9; (1937) 179; (1940) 403, 405 n.1
Stewart (2008) 63-67 figs III.1-III.9
Stylianou (1997) 28
Van Deun (1993) 115-9
Whitehouse (2009) 252-260
Yon (1993) 140; (1997) 283

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Catalogue number	64	Location	Soloi (Soli)	Map reference	35.12.47 N 33.27.43 E
Identification/ dedication	Auxibios?	Date	Late 4th – late 6th c	District	Kyrenia

Auxibios was the first bishop of Soloi (62-112). Here he was baptised and/or underwent ordination by John Mark. The basilica, which probably bore his name and received his remains, lay about 200m to the east of the ancient and Late Antique port city on the north coast. Set on a parterre raised on the north and cut into the hillside to the south, there is evidence for five structures on the site, the last two of which can be identified as basilical. Basilica A is dated on numismatic evidence (Valens, Gratian and Theodosius) to the mid-fourth century. Basilica B is early fifth to mid-seventh century. An inscription from the atrium records repairs, including to the roof, undertaken by a Bishop John in 655 following the invasions of 649 and 650. The site was excavated by the University of Laval (Québec) under des Gagniers and Tinh between 1964 and 1974.

Structure 1

According to the *Vita* of Heraclidus the saint ‘having prayed, marked out the form of the church by drawing a great one by his grace,’ and this is the church that St Auxibios ‘started to build.’ This may have been the building identified by Neal as Structure 1 which consisted of a rectangular room with an eastern apse, about 10.5m wide and 17.75m long (including the apse). Its floor lay 4.25m below Basilicas A and B and its apsidal east end may have been incorporated into Basilica B determining the size of its northern apsidiole, indeed the doorway which opens in it may have originated as a window in the apse of Structure 1.

Structure 2

On the north side of Basilica B was a second rectangular room, divided in two by responds, which also concluded in an eastern apse. It was about 7m wide and 19.1m long including the apse. This building was incorporated into Basilica B, the north wall of which partly rested in the south wall of Structure 2.

Structure 3

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This can only be identified by the mosaic floor exposed in the outer angle of the central apse and south apsidiole of Basilica B and which can also be seen through the floor of its apse [64.1]. The apse of Basilica B, therefore, was constructed on a pre-existing mosaic floor of a rectangular building, at least 8.8m in its north-south dimension, of which the mosaics are the fragmentary remains. It is possible that the inscription in a *tabula ansata* - 'O Christ, help the one who gave [or dedicated] this mosaic,' (ΧΡΙΣΤΕ ΒΟΘΕΙ/ ΤΩ ΨΗΦΩCAN/ΤΕΙ) - marks the entrance to Structure 3 because it was clearly intended to be read facing east [64.2]. Megaw argued that this mosaic constituted the only mosaic floor in Basilica B on the grounds that it was on the same level as the sixth-century *opus sectile* surrounding the sanctuary. Michaelides implies a fourth-century date, comparing it with the plain interlace circles round with the mosaic fronting the apse at Chrysopolitissa. However, Neal argues for a different structure altogether which predates Basilicas A and B because the inscription lies 0.7m south of the axis of Basilica A's processional way.

Basilica A

Basilica A may be the best evidence, not for a *domus ecclesia* as Stewart suggests but for an *aula ecclesia*. A particularly puzzling feature of the basilica is the three semi-circular basins, 1.9m across and 0.78m deep, which formed the basilica's eastern extent. They probably held water because they were rendered with hydraulic plaster with a stone *thalassa* in the pavement below [64.3]. These basins together with the ambiguous nature of the mosaics led Megaw to doubt that Basilica A, which he dated to 330, was a Christian building. He identified the basins with a nymphaeum and therefore 'surely incompatible with a Christian church,' despite Christos' identification of the Nymphaeum at Kourion as having been, albeit temporarily, adapted for Christian purposes. Tinh suggested that the basins were not Roman but played their part in the liturgy because, otherwise, they would not have survived, suggesting that the *thalassa* served for the evacuation of water used at the altar.

Basilica A was orientated 20° south of east. It was a five-aisled basilica, raised on 48 timber posts supporting timber architraves, with a floor area of c.1270 sq.m [64.4]. The width of the central aisle was 7.25m wide and the aisles were 4.5m wide. The relative narrowness of the nave and the relative width of the aisles together with their division by four rows of 12 columns, would have given its interior something of the look of a hypostyle hall which in a later phase Neal described 'a 'forest' of posts [64.5]. Although

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Basilica A was about 46m long its width is more difficult to determine. A possible clue may be the ramp in the north aisle, probably 11m long and descending 4.25m to Structure 1's floor level which, according to Neal, may represent that building's incorporation into Basilica A, and possibly, therefore, indicating the position of its north wall [64.6]. If the processional way marked out in mosaic in its central aisle is axial the Basilica must have been about 27.5m across.

The supports were 2.70m apart but between the sixth and seventh supports the gap widened to 3.6m. Megaw proposed a transverse aisle at this point. Extrapolating from the excavated material, he argued that, had the smaller intercolumniations continued eastwards by another six bays it would have coincided with the eastern limit of the mosaic floor. He went on to propose a nave altar at the intersection between the processional way and this wider 'middle' bay. That would be why, he argued, attempts at finding the altar of Basilica A by excavating through the sanctuary floor of Basilica B proved unproductive. Late-fourth century Chrysopolitissa may offer the closest parallel. There too the altar was close to the centre of the building. Moreover, in Phase 1 at both sites no distinction was made between the levels of the mosaic floor in the sanctuary and the remainder of the building. A later-phase sanctuary, 5m by 4m, can be identified by moulded bases set directly onto the mosaic floor. The central of the three basins connected by the *thalassa* would have been included in the sanctuary with the north and south basins falling outside it.

Neal proposed a further phase in which the posts were removed and replaced by stone piers at 3.65 centres creating a sanctuary 16m long by 15m wide including all three basins [64.7-8]. In a later phase still, probably in the fifth or early sixth centuries, the sanctuary became a raised bema. Its construction involved the demolition of part of the east wall containing the basins. The central basin survived in the bema floor but because the new north and south walls of the bema projected westwards from the north edge of the south basin and the south edge of the north basin, these outer basins did not. This bema, 5.9m by 10.20m, was raised 0.90m above the mosaic floor. Its pavement provides the first use of *opus sectile* on the site. Later still the bema was enlarged again to 16.20m by 9.30m and provided with an apsidal east end. Posts and *plutae* enclosed what was now a circumambulatory bema which Neal suggests would have been higher at its east end. It is likely that the new bema too would have been paved in *opus sectile*.

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The foundations of the 4m sq. canopy covering the altar have been identified; in the earliest phases it is possible that the altar was portable.

The floor of Basilica A was paved with about 150 square and rectangular mosaic panels. However, there is considerable variation in what survives in the nave north of the processional way and what survives to the south of it. The processional way was defined by a series of panels, 0.95m square, which only survive in the western half of the nave, hence nothing survives of the treatment of the wider central bay. On the north side, but still within the nave, the panels are approximately square and divided north-south by thin compartments corresponding to the piers. On the south side of the processional way there are no such compartments and the correspondence is between whole panels and posts.

The contrast is most marked in the treatment of the aisles. Nothing remains of the floor of the north outer aisle. The north inner was divided into approximately square panels and may date from the early-fifth century. While the remainder of the floor is geometrical, animals are prominent here, including ducks and waterfowl [64.9], dolphins [64.10] and, the best known, a swan [64.11]. Of the surviving panels, the two westernmost (bays 2 and 3) were intended to be viewed looking west, and the two easternmost (bays 5 and 6) were intended to be seen looking east. The panel between them (bay 4) is both more complex in design than the remainder of the units in this aisle and is, arguably, coarser in treatment. It entirely lacks the animals which are such a feature of the remaining panels, rather cross motifs predominate in what looks like a conscious break with the pattern established by the panels in the immediate vicinity (c.f. a strikingly similar arrangement at Aquileia). What remains of the panels of the south inner aisle broadly corresponds to double bays except at the west end where two panels correspond to single bays. The southernmost aisle contains the most extensive remains. While the correspondence between the posts and panels is here at its most arbitrary, there may have been an attempt to distinguish between those panels corresponding to the nave and those corresponding to the sanctuary. In which case the nave was defined by two square panels followed by two panels extending across approximately three bays each, respectively 7.15m and 8.20m long, followed by two more square bays. Aligned with what may have been the western edge of the chancel is a thin panel orientated north-south with a décor of columns and crosses possibly marking the western limit of a quasi-*parabema* in the south aisle much as the processional way constructs a quasi-

solea [64.12]. Overall, the décor of the south outer aisle draws on a less complex vocabulary than elsewhere in the floor, using conspicuously larger tesserae and including considerable amounts of ceramic, some used on *en face*, some on edge [64.13].

Basilica B

Basilica B was orientated 25° south of east. This was the largest three-aisled, triapsidal basilica on the island [64.14]. It was 54m long (including the apse) by 33.5m across, with a floor area of about 1460 sq.m and lateral walls 0.60m thick. The basilica's east wall terminated in a projecting central apse 9.6m across and 4.9m deep with walls 2.2m thick, two apsidioles, 4.8m across and 2.2m deep, and two straight 'shoulders' [64.15]. Interapsidal passages connected the central apse and the apsidioles [64.16-18] and, in addition, there were three doorways in the east wall, one in each of the straight 'shoulders' and one in the north apsidiole, possibly the window from Structure 1 [64.19]. Eleven columns separated the nave from each aisle. Each column was 1.05m at the base narrowing to 0.90m and about 6.3m tall. They were set on 1.30m sq bases that were spaced between 2.2m and 2.7m apart. Because the columns were assembled from limestone drums from different quarries they would have been rendered and painted (c.f. Agios Epiphanius) [64.20]. The capitals carried a simple moulding and varied in height from 0.60m to 0.83m and they may, therefore, have been *spolia*. The colonnades were aligned with 4.5m long projections from the west wall that probably served as buttressing. At the east end the colonnades concluded with demi-shafts notably smaller than the diameter of the full columns. The walls were constructed from carefully worked ashlar laid header-and-stretcher fashion, which was probably intended to have a decorative effect, at least on the exterior (cf Aphendrika) [64.21]. In the interior, niches articulated the lateral walls. There were two semi-circular niches in the north wall [64.22] and six, alternately rectangular and semi-circular, in the south wall where they were framed by shallow pilaster strips [64.23]. Fourth-century Apa Shenute in Egypt has exactly the same scheme (cf also sixth-century Dendera). At both sites the niches were crowned with semi-domes and the same may have been the case at Soloi.

At some point, possibly in the later sixth century, the circumambulatory bema was extended north and south to fill the full width of the nave and eastwards to fill the formerly empty apse. The floor level of the bema in the apse was raised in part to allow

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for a very narrow, barrel-vaulted, *kyklion* (only 0.45m wide) beneath the upper tier of the *synthronon* that now lined the wall of the apse [64.24-5].

The floor of the south aisle of Basilica B is likely to have been paved in marmara and the nave and the north aisle of were paved in *opus sectile*. All evidence for the designs in the nave was removed in order to expose the mosaics of Basilica A. However, in the north aisle the mortar setting for the *crustae* shows clearly that there were three rows each of 13 panels with slightly longer panels corresponding to the western edge of the bema. The centre row was wider and the northern row established an 'aisle' corresponding to the doorway in the straight section of wall at the east end. The outer rows may have had the same design and there is evidence that the second set of panels from the west may have been given a distinctive treatment corresponding to a doorway in the north wall accessing a rectangular room with benches against its north wall [64.26].

The basilica was preceded by a narthex doubling as the east portico of an atrium, 15.4m by 18.3m and supported on piers. Each portico was 3.35m wide and paved in *opus sectile*. The narthex pavement was distinguished from the floor in the incompletely excavated north and south porticoes by the square slab at centre of each panel [64.27]. T-shaped piers at the eastern corners of the atrium and corresponding pilasters in the north and south porticoes were probably joined by arches which served further to distinguish the narthex. The piers defining the narthex were also more widely spaced, particularly opposite the west doorway into the basilica. The final distinguishing feature was the apsidal-ended exedra terminating the narthex north and south [64.28-29] (cf Agios Epiphanius and Campanopetra). A northern entrance to the complex was adjacent to the north exedra. The upper three steps into the atrium may have belonged to a much longer flight of stairs on the evidence of the tread now at pavement level, which before the remainder of the floor level was raised, may have been comparable with the monumental staircase at Campanopetra [64.30]. There is no corresponding entrance to the south because this part of the building was cut into the bedrock but to a height considerably lower than the present ground level because a window head survives in the south exedra [64.31]. A bench was built against the north wall of the north portico, west of the principal entrance and there is evidence that benches may have been a feature of the north portico [64.32]. Gold and glass tesserae found in this portico suggest that the entry into the basilica would have been embellished with an impressive décor. The court too was paved in mosaic, including in the southeast corner, peacocks, other birds,

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and possibly a horse, set in octagonal frames (cf Timvou). In the centre of the atrium there was a hexagonal fountain with semi-circular niches on the exterior, set on a rectangular platform but closer to the axis of Basilica A rather than B. Neal identifies this as the baptismal pool but on what evidence is unclear.

Bibliography

<i>AJA</i>	(1970) 75; (1975) 132; (1968) 376-377; (1970) 396
<i>AR</i>	(1970) 53
<i>ARDA</i>	(1967) 14; (1969) 18; (1970) 15; (1972) 20; (1973) 23-4; (1974) 28-9; (1975) 27
des Gagniers/Tinh	(1985)
des Gagniers	(1975) 222-232
Feisel	(1978) 380-381
Gunnis	(1936) 162, 257, 376
Hogarth	(1889) 113
Megaw	(1974) 64-5; (1976) 12; (1997) 343-352 at 348, fig. 5; (2001) 171-180
Michaelides	(1992) 7, 67 no.34, 77 no.42
Mitford	(1950) 150-154
Neal	(2010)
Noret	(1986) 445-452
Papacostas	(1995) Gazetteer 14; (1999) II 72, III fig 231
Papageorghiou	(1965) 96; (1985) 311-32; (1986-88) 167-88; (2002) 63-70
Pliny/Rackham	(1942) 319
Stewart	(2008) II. 31-2, 222n.16

Catalogue number	65	Location	Souni (Σουνι)	Map reference	No data
Identification/dedication	<i>Chiliantri</i>	Date	6th-7th c	District	Limassol

At Souni-*Chiliantri*, north of Kourion, the Department of Antiquities excavated a single-aisled chapel, 5.7m by 4.15m, with an inscribed apse and a semi-covered porch. To the north, the lowest part of the building was carved into the bedrock while the southern part was raised on a foundation of large stones. Fallen masonry to the north and east of the church suggests that the basilica was part of a much larger and possibly monastic complex. The site was occupied until the seventh century.

Bibliography

<i>ARDA</i>	(2003) 48-9
<i>BCH</i>	(1997) 929-30

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Catalogue number	66	Location	Aphendrika (Galinoporni)	Map reference	31.25.20 N 29.56.33 E
Identification/ dedication	Panagia Sykha	Date	6th c.	District	Famagusta

The basilica lies 15km south-west of Aphendrika and Asomatos at a place also called Aphendrika. Megaw identified Sykha together with Panagia Aphendrika and Asomatos as a distinctive group. Oriented 25° north of east it had approximately the same groundplan, size and proportions as Asomatos, although Gunnis gives the measurements as '78 feet by 45 feet,' almost exactly the size and proportions of Aphendrika. Enlart calculated the internal length as 15.25m long but he included the later narthex, which like Aphendrika and Asomatos, was not part of the original layout. Megaw and Hawkins give a length of 12.30m, a nave width of 4.80m and a proportion of 1:2.56 [66.1-2].

Sykha was a wooden-roofed, three-aisled basilica with a triapsidal east end, each apse semi-circular internally and externally [66.3]. There were no interapsidal passages. Each colonnade consisted of four limestone shafts with demi-columns serving as responds making five intercolumniations of 2.46m [66.4]. The responds were constructed from drums, about 55cm across, the evidence for three of which survives [66.5-7]. The aisles were c.2.4m wide and the main apse was 4.3m at cord. A step effected the transition from the thinner lateral walls to the thicker walls of the apses which presumably carried semi-domes. The west wall and the lower part of the apses survive, of which the southern apsidiole is the best preserved. The basilica was constructed from well-finished blocks of local limestone laid header and stretcher fashion in the usual c.50cm deep courses, which were reinforced when the building was vaulted. Megaw and Hawkins suggest the three-stepped synthronon was integral to the construction, making Sykha the last in the group. Fragments of a marble ambo and chancel screen panels recovered from the nave presumably also belonged to the original plan [66.8]. An apsidal ended ancillary space was attached to the south aisle which Stewart suggested may have served as a martyrium.

Bibliography

- AD* (1965) 615
ARDA (1966) 9, 42
BCH (1965) 298-300

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Enlart	(1987) 304-8, 414
Gunnis	(1936), 167-8, 414
Jeffery	(1918) 257-8
Bardswell	(1938-9) 404-8
Megaw	(1946) 48-56
Megaw/Hawkins	(1977) 24
Papacostas	(1999) II 74, III fig 233
Papageorghiou	(1965) 94; (1966) 221; (1965) 94; (1968) 8; (1982), 438-39
Sotirou	(1931) 8, 482 (1935) figs 4, 5, pls. 10a, 11a,b, 12a,b, 13a, 15a
Stewart	(2008) 41-49; (2010) 164-174

Catalogue number	67	Location	Syngrasis (Sinirüstü)	Map reference	35.12.48 E 33.28.39N
Identification/dedication	Ayios Procopius	Date	Mid 6th c.	District	Famagusta

Oriented 25° north of east, the now-derelict church of Ayios Procopius provides evidence for a mid-sixth century basilica: (1) the apse is lined with a synthronon, 246 cm across and 140cm deep, now wholly rendered and consisting of four steps with no axial projection [67.1]; (2) inset in the bema are eleven panels of *opus sectile*, all reset as standardized units [67.2], and (3) there is one complete Proconnesian column and two fragments in the north-east corner of the churchyard. Their widths, 29-30 cm at their narrowest, are comparable with two more examples in the chapel above and a little to the west of the village. However, because Proconnesian columns were exported as standard lengths it cannot be assumed that the columns at the chapel site belong with those at the basilica. Gunnis noted ‘small portion of a well-cut inscription of the Byzantine period, and two Corinthian capitals; a large cippus with a hollow top is used as a font.’

Bibliography

ARDA	(1954) 12 (1955) 12
Chatzechristophe	(1997) 279-80
Gunnis	(1936) 434-5
Hadjisavas	(1991) 46, 59, 94, 96
Jeffery	(1918) 241
Papacostas	(1999) I 69, 156 II fig 228
Soteriou	(1931) 484; (1935) pl.39a

3: Gazetteer

Catalogue number	68	Location	Tamassos/Politiko	Map reference	33.14.30 N 35.01.30 E
Identification/dedication	Ayios Heracleidios	Date	Mid-4th and 5th c.	District	Nicosia

The Episcopal basilica is situated on the outskirts of Politiko, on the west bank of the Pediaios River, close to the ancient/Late Antique city of Tamassos. The mausoleum/martyrium of Herkleidios, one of the settlement's earliest bishops and a disciple of Barnabas, was a pilgrimage site from the fourth century and in the fifth century a wooden roofed columnar basilica, preceded by a narthex and an atrium was erected adjacent to it. Excavations began in 1963. The form of the mid-fourth century martyrium has yet to be established, but it is possibly connected with the Greco-Roman tomb, the dromo of which Papageorghiou excavated outside the apse of the basilica during the restoration of 1964. The same campaign exposed a fifth or sixth century mosaic floor in the north aisle which had been substantially destroyed by the large number of later tombs inserted through it. Had the basilica been destroyed by fire during an Arab raid in the seventh century, as Papageorghiou proposed, it would represent a remarkably deep penetration of the interior.

Bibliography

<i>AR</i>	(1966) 42
<i>ARDA</i>	(1965) 11; (2010) 27
<i>BCH</i>	(1965) 297-98
Halkin	(1964) 133-69
Jeffery	(1918) 212-14
Megaw	(1976) 9
Michaelides	(1993) 75 fig. 40
Papageorghiou	(1965) 38-43; (1965-66) 12-3; (1966) 221; (1975) 190-1; (1982) 469; (1986) 490, 502; (1993) 46
Papacostas	(1995) Gazetteer 15d; (1999) II 36-37; III 116-7
Pliny/Rackham	(1942) 319
Stewart	(2008) 39-40
van Esbroeck	(1985) 115-62

Catalogue number	69	Location	Kirklar (Timvou)	Map reference	35.7.15 N 33.31.0 E
Identification/dedication	Agio Saranta (Kirklar Tekkesi)	Date	5th-6th c	District	Nicosia

According to Gunnis,

This is one of the strangest monuments still remaining on the Island. From it steps lead down into a vast cave consisting of a central nave and two side aisles, the dividing walls pierced by round arches. It is the size and plan of a large church, the central nave ending in an apse, while the side aisles terminate in square chambers; small apertures in the roof admit the light.

The village of Kirkklar and the basilica of Agio Saranta to the south of it lie within a Turkish base. Because requests to visit were refused by the military authorities this report is indebted to Foulis' description.

A Hellenistic and Roman rock cut chamber with *loculi* at the sides was enlarged to give the appearance of a substantial three-aisled basilica. In 2007 a small three-aisled basilica was discovered in the west court of the tekke above the underground 'basilica'. Its bema was raised above the nave by two steps and was enclosed by a stone screen [69.1]. Both the bema and the nave were paved with mosaic. The bema pavement consisted of five octagons framed with a double-stranded guilloche in tesserae of black, white, brown and violet [69.2]. Each of the octagons, together with the remaining trapezoidal spaces were inhabited by animals including a deer, a standing lioness [69.3], a cuttlefish [69.4], a bear attacking a deer, two aquatic birds, a swan attacking a snake with a ram occupying the central octagon. The nave mosaic, largely geometric and floral, may belong to an earlier phase of the building [69.5-6]. Foulis dates the mosaics of the bema to the first half of the sixth century and those of the nave to the fifth century, pointing out that both pavements attest to a hitherto unrecognised penetration of the hinterland by the kind of high quality production more usually associated with the littoral (cf Tamassos)

Bibliography

Foulis	(2008) 3-24 figs 1-43; (2012) 381-389
Gunnis	(1936) 453
Hackett	(1901) 421
Luke/Jardine	(1913) 47

3: Gazetteer

Catalogue number	70	Location	Thronoi	Map reference	Close to Cape Pyla
Identification/dedication	No data	Date	No data	District	Larnaca

The ancient settlement survived to the beginning of the middle ages. Remnants of a basilica have been located on the coast in the region of Ayia Thekla but not excavated. Fragments of a chancel screen were recovered from the site.

Bibliography

Papageorghiou (1993) 28, 40

Catalogue number	71	Location	Tremetousia (Erdemli)	Map reference	35.5.1 N 33.26.28 E
Identification/dedication	Ayios Spyridon	Date	Late 4th, early 5th c	District	Larnaca

The basilica is now on a Turkish military base and requests to visit were refused. Spyridon (270-348) was born Tremetousia, the site of ancient Trimitos, and became its bishop, attended the Council of Nicaea in 325. The basilica which bears his name and contained his relics, was identified in the reading of the *Vita* given on the saint's feast day on 14th December 655 by its author, Theodorus Bishop of Paphos, who described wall paintings relating to the Life and Miracles of the Saint but he made no mention of the destruction of the basilica. The pilgrimage church was originally a modest wooden-roofed, three-aisled, columnar basilica, c.25 by 17.5 covering an area of about 440 sq.m. [71.1]. On the evidence of the stone bases which supported the columns it is likely that these too were stone. Its early date was ascertained during the excavations in the 1960s when Papagiorgiou discovered the original mosaic floor and an inscription,

ΨΗ ΦΙ [ΔΙΓΡΑ ΠΤΗ] ΠΟΙΚΙΑΝΤΑΙ ΤΗΝ ΧΡΟΑΝ
ΤΟΠΟΝ ΚΟΣΜΗΣΑΙ ΑΓΙΩΝ ΕΠΙΣΚΟΠΩΝ
ΚΑΡΤΑΙΡΙΟΥ ΧΕΡΣΙΝ ΠΡΟΣΕΤΑΞΕΝ ΑΓΑΘΕΣ
ΜΝΗΜΗΣ ΣΦΥΡΙΔΩΝ ΜΕΤΑΙΧΩΝ ΑΓΙΑΣ
ΙΣΟΣ ΟΜΟΙΩ ΔΥΝΑΜΙ ΠΝΕΥΜΑΤΙΚΗ+

3: Gazetteer

Multicoloured tesserae adorn as decoration

The Church of the Holy Bishops, by the hands of

Karterios who instructed,

And by Dyridon who, being equal and endowed

With similar vigour, shares their pious memory+ [71.2]

The style of the mosaic surrounding the inscription and the epigraphy belong to the late fourth century. Part of the mosaic pavement in the apse was destroyed and replaced by an *opus sectile* floor and a second *opus sectile* floor was found in a building adjacent to the basilica.

Bibliography

- | | |
|---------------|--|
| <i>AJA</i> | (1968) 379, pl. 126, fig. 32 |
| <i>BCH</i> | (1967) 365 |
| Gunnis | (1936) 443-44 |
| Jeffery | (1918) 182 |
| Megaw | (1976) 9 |
| Michaelides | (1993) 75 fig.16 |
| Mouriki | (1993) 241-2 |
| Papacostas | (1999) II 73; III fig 232 |
| Papageorghiou | (1965-6) 15-21; (1966) 17-33 pl.IX-XIII; (1967-8) 3-4; (1968a) 16;
(1969) 222-25; (1975) 191; (1993) 39 |
| Stewart | (2008) 39-40 |
| Van den Ven | (1953) 143-156 |

1 Akamas: Ayios Kononas

- | | | |
|--|---|--|
| 1 Akamas: Ayios Kononas | 24 Kalavastos: Area II | 47 Paphos: Chrysopolitissa |
| 2 Akanthou / Tatlisu:
Panagia Pergameniotissa | 25 Kalavastos: Area V | 48 Paphos: Panagia
Limeniotissa |
| 3 Akrotiri: Katalymmata
ton Plakoton | 26 Kalavastos- <i>Sirmata</i> | 49 Paphos: Shyrvallos |
| 4 Akrotiri: Lania | 27 Karpas: Ayios Philon | 50 Paphos: Toumballos |
| 5 Alassa: Ayia Mavri | 28 Kellia | 51 Peyia: Baptistery basilica |
| 6 Amathus:
Acropolis basilica | 29 Kiti: Angeloktisti | 52 Peyia: Central basilica |
| 7 Amathus: Ayios Tykhonas | 30 Knidos | 53 Peyia: North basilica |
| 8 Amathus: Episcopal
basilica | 31 Kourion: Baptistery
basilica | 54 Peyia: South basilica |
| 9 Amathus: South-west
basilica | 32 Kourion: Episcopal
basilica | 55 Polis: <i>Arsinoe</i> (EG0) |
| 10 Amathus: Ayia Varvara | 33 Kourion: Extra-mural
basilica | 56 Polis: <i>Chrysochous</i> (EF2) |
| 11 Aphenrika: Asomatos | 34 Kourion: Limeniotissa | 57 Pyla: <i>Koutsopetria</i> |
| 12 Aphenrika: Panagia | 35 Kourion: Nymphaeum
basilica | 58 Rizokarpaso / Dipkarpaz |
| 13 Ayia Moni | 36 Lambousa / Lapithos /
Lapta: Acheiropoietos | 59 Salamis: Agios Epifanios |
| 14 Choirokoitia: Panagia tou
Kambou | 37 Limassol: Tychikos /
Nemesios | 60 Salamis: Agios Varnavas |
| 15 Episkopi: Saraya | 38 Livadia / Sazliköy:
Panagia tis Kyras | 61 Salamis: Campanopetra |
| 16 Germasoyeia- <i>Kalogeroi</i> | 39 Lysi / Akdoğan: Panagia | 62 Salamis: Forum basilica |
| 17 Geronisos | 40 Lythrankomi / Boltasli:
Panagia Kanakariá | 63 Salamis: Hagiasma of
Nicodemus |
| 18 Geroskipou: Agioi Pente | 41 Marathovouno / Ulukisla | 64 Soloi |
| 19 Gialousa-Sipahi / Yeni
Erenköy: Ayia Trias | 42 Maroni- <i>Petrera</i> | 65 Souni- <i>Chiliantri</i> |
| 20 Gialousa-Sipahi / Yeni
Erenköy: Chtomólia | 43 Mazōtos- <i>Petounta</i> | 66 Sykha: Panayia |
| 21 Gialousa / Yeni Erenköy:
Agios Phōtios | 44 Morphou / Güzelyurt:
Agios Mamas | 67 Syngrasis / Sinirüstü:
Ayios Procopius |
| 22 Golgoi | 45 Nicosia: Bedestan | 68 Tamassos: Ayios
Heracleidios |
| 23 Idalion | 46 Nicosia: St. George's Hill | 69 Timvou / Kirklar: Agio
Saranta |
| | | 70 Thronoi |
| | | 71 Tremetousia / Erdemli:
Ayios Spyridon |

1 Akamas: Ayios Kononas

1.1 Plan
(after Fejfer 1995)

1.2 Capital
(Fejfer 1995)

1.3 Resited closure screen
(Fejfer 1995)

2.1 East end of Middle Byzantine church looking southwest

2.2 Arch springer

2.3 Column

2.4 South apsidiole, with east respond of south colonnade and inter-apsidal passage, looking east

2.5 Inter-apsidal passage between the south apsidiole and the central apse looking east

2.6 Feature in east wall of south apsidiole looking east

3.1 Plan (after Procopiou 2009)

3.2 Site looking southwest

3.3 Central apse looking northeast

3.4 Mosaic fragment from central apse

3.5 Reliquary lid

3.6 South apsidiole in transept west wall, looking northwest. *Mensa martyris*

3.7 Apse in south wall of transept looking southwest

3.8 East ambulatory of south transept looking south

3.9 Clasping buttress. Junction of south aisle and south transept arm, looking southeast

3.10 Mosaic pavement

3.11 Mosaic pavement

3.12 Central apse looking northwest

3.13 North annex looking west

5.1 Plan (after Flourentzos 1996)

5.2 Site (Flourentzos 1996)

5.3 Basilica looking southeast

5.4 Nave looking east

5.5 North aisle looking east

5.6 Threshold at north end of narthex looking south

5.7 Pavement of north aisle looking west

5.8 Inscription. Junction of the north aisle and narthex

5.9 Apse embedded in later masonry looking northwest

5.10 Impost block from the apse incorporated in later pier on the south side of the nave

6.1 Site plan (after Aupert 1998)

6.2 Basilica. Plan

6 Amathus: Acropolis basilica

6.3 North colonnade looking southeast

6.4 Central apse looking northwest

6 Amathus: Acropolis basilica

6.5 Site of altar and central apse looking southeast

6.6 Site of ambo and north colonnade looking west

6 Amathus: Acropolis basilica

6.7 Site of altar looking west

6.8 Nave. *Opus sectile* paving. State in 1984

6.9 Bench lining north wall of north aisle looking west

6.10 Nave. *Opus sectile* paving looking southeast

6.11 Nave. Central strip of *opus sectile* paving looking west

6.12 Paving of apse of north annex

6.13 Bench against west wall of annex attached to the north of the narthex

6.14 Isometric reconstruction (Aupert 1998)

7.1 Phase 1. Plan (after Aupert 1998)

7.2 Corridor looking north

7.3 Rectangular niche in west wall of corridor

7.4 Polygonal apse looking northwest

7 Amathus: Ayios Tykhonas

7.5 Phase 2. Plan (after Aupert 1998)

7.6 Interior looking west

7.7 Interior looking north

7.8 Three apses on the north side of the basilica looking east

8 Amathus: Episcopal basilica

8.1 Plan (after Aupert 1998)

8.2 Site looking east

8 Amathus: Episcopal basilica

8.3 Nave looking west

8.4 Theodosian capitals

8 Amathus: Episcopal basilica

8.5 Atrium and basilica looking east

8.6 Room with bench to the north of north aisle, looking west

9 Amathus: Southwest basilica

9.2 Site looking southeast

9 Amathus: Southwest basilica

9.3 Narthex with bench and raised exonarthex looking northwest

9.4 Nave looking west

9.5 Bema and altar
looking southeast

9.6 South annex
looking east

10.1 Apses looking north

10.2 Sarcophagus. Site looking east

10.3 Interment looking northeast

10.4 Mosaic pavement. Inhabited trellis. Looking south

10.5 Mosaic pavement.
Poised squares.
Looking east

10.6 Monastic buildings looking southeast

11.1 Plan (after Megaw 1946)

11.2 Basilica looking southeast

11.3 East end looking south

11.4 Column base

11.5 Stylobate of north colonnade looking northeast

11.6 Junction of south wall of nave and apse. Embedded demi-shaft

11.7 Columns from columnar basilica in the foundations of pier basilica. North wall

11.8 Step between the lateral wall and the south apsidiole, looking northwest

11.9 Looking north through the interapsidal passage ways

11.10 Synthronon looking southeast

11.11 South aisle looking east

11.12 Nave, north wall. Embedded closure screen post

12.1 Plan (after Megaw 1946)

12.2 Site looking west

12.3 Embedded demi-column. East end of south colonnade, looking northeast

12.4 Wallwork. South outer wall. Detail

12.5 South wall looking north

12.6 Northeast quadrant of main apse looking northeast

12.7 North and central apses looking south

12.8 Southeast quadrant of north apsidiole with intersidal passage, looking southeast

12.9 Intersidal passage between the central apse and the north apsidiole, looking north

12.10 Central apse.
Remains of synthronon

12.11 Chancel screen curbing
reused in later basilica,
looking north

13.1 North east corner of later basilica

14.1 Site looking west (Dept of Antiquities)

15.1 Site looking east

15.2 Pavement at east end (Megaw 2007)

18.1 Apse looking south

18.2 Tomb slab looking west

19.1 Plan (after Papagerghiou 1986)

19.2 Looking east. Condition in 2009

19.3 Looking east. Condition in 1971

19.4 Basilica looking northeast

19.5 North colonnade looking northeast

19.6 Bema looking northeast

19.7 Bema stairs and east end of solea looking east

19.8 Intercolumnial screens, north colonnade looking northwest

19.9 Solea looking east

19.10 Solea post

19.11 East end of *solea*. Columnar entrance and panel looking northeast

19.12 North end of narthex looking north

19.13 'Straight' east end of north annex looking south

19.14 Possible south *katechumenaion* looking west. Route obstructed by later apse

19.15 Inscription inside central doorway, looking east

19.16 Off-centre inscription at the foot of the bema looking southeast

19.17 'Rainbow' panel and processional way looking west

19.18 Nave. Detail of second frame of pavement

19.19 Nave. Northeast corner of the inner frame of pavement

19.20 South aisle. Pavement looking west

19.21 North aisle. Pavement looking east

19.22 North aisle looking west. Detail of second panel

19.23 West respond of south colonnade looking southwest

19.24 Pavement of south exedra and narthex looking north

19.25 Narthex. Circular motif looking west

19.26 Pavement of possible south entrance to complex

21.1 Northeast quadrant of apse, west of Middle Byzantine church, looking southwest

21.2 Foundation of apse and Middle Byzantine church looking south

22.1 Plan (after Bakirtzis 1976)

24.1 Plan (after Rautman 2003)

24.2 Basilica looking east

24.3 Northern mural apse looking south

24.4 Central apse looking west

24.5 Bema looking east

24.6 Apsidal annex attached to the south aisle, looking west

24.7 Annex to east of south aisle looking northwest

25.1 Plan (after Rautman 2003)

25.2 East end looking south (Rautman 1994)

25.3 Apse. *Opus sectile* floor (Rautman 2003)

26.1 Plan (after Rautman 2003)

26.2 Central apse looking east

26.3 Central apse. Axial stairs and clergy bench looking northeast

26.4 Narthex looking southwest

26.5 Bench in northwest corner of narthex looking northwest

26.6 Stairway in subterranean chamber at south end of narthex looking northeast

26.7 Stairs leading from the north aisle to the courtyard to the north of the basilica, looking north

27.1 Plan (after du Plat Taylor and Megaw 1981)

27.2 Harbour. East mole looking west

27.3 North apse looking southwest

27.4 *Opus sectile* pavement at south end of narthex, looking east

27.5 Position of north colonnade looking east

27.6 *Opus sectile*-paved corridor looking north. Narthex?

27.7 *Phiale* in south atrium looking east

27.8 Plan of excavated area of atrium and the structure to its east (after du Plat Taylor and Megaw 1981)

27.9 East portico of atrium looking northeast

28.1 East end
looking north

28.2 Junction of south
apsidiole and central
apse looking west

29.1 East end looking southwest

29.2 Granite column

29.3 Proconnesian chancel screen post

32.1 Plan (after Megaw 2007)

32.2 Site looking west

32.3 Atrium looking southwest

32.4 North entrance looking north (Megaw 2007)

32.5 Forum entrance looking west

32.6 Polygonal apse looking northwest

32.7 South colonnade looking southeast

32.8 South *pastophoria* looking west

32.9 North *pastophoria* looking west

32.10 Focus in east court looking northeast

32.11 North *katechumenaion* looking east

32.12 South *katechumenaion* looking east

32.13 North *katechumenaion*. Bench

32.14 Narthex looking south

32.15 North aisle. Looking south. *Opus sectile* pavement.

32.16 Solea. Post

32.17 Champlévé half pediment (Megaw 2007)

32.18 Possible *diakonikon* looking northeast

32.19 Ground floor of *episkopion* looking west

32.20 North wall of *diakonikon* looking northeast

32.21 Inscription at entrance to *diakonikon* looking west

33.1 Plan (after Papageorgiou 1986)

33.2 Basilica looking northeast

33.3 Reused seating in the north wall looking northeast

33.4 Bema looking east

33.5 Corridor attached to the north aisle looking west

33.6 Apsidal-ended annex north of 33.5, looking west

33.7 Aligned doorways between the apsidal-ended annex and north aisle, looking north

33.8 South annex looking east

33.9 South entrance to atrium looking north

33.10 North entrance to atrium looking north

34.1 Site looking southeast

34.2 Polygonal central apse looking west

34.3 South apsidiole with partition looking west

34.4 Feature in south apsidiole looking west

34.5 South colonnade looking east

34.6 Bema looking northeast

34.7 Bema. *Opus sectile* paving. Detail

34.8 Narthex looking north

34.9 Atrium looking south

34.10 Possible north entrance to atrium looking north

35.1 Plan (after Christou 2007)

35.2 Site looking southeast

35.3 Apse looking southwest

35.4 'Nave' looking northwest

35.5 Nymphaeum looking northwest

36.1 Plan (after Soteriou 1935)

36.2 Site looking southwest

36.3 Iconostasis with spoliated columns, capitals and closure screen (Soteriou 1935)

36.4 *Opus sectile* paving to the northeast of the site

37.1 Plan (after Dept. of Antiquities)

37.2

37.2 South apsidiole looking south

38.1 Plan (after Megaw and Hawkins 1971)

38.2 Site looking northwest

38.3 Mosaic fragment in the east wall south of apse looking southeast

38.4 Reused chancel screen post, looking northeast

38.5 Sanctuary. Junction of north wall and apse, looking northeast

38.6 Sanctuary. Junction of south wall and apse, looking southeast

38.7 Limestone column

38.8 Press

39.1 Plan (after Papageorgiou 1964)

40.1 Plan (after Megaw and Hawkins 1977)

40.2 Basilica. East end

40.3 Porch looking northeast

40.4 Base

40.5 Capital

40.6 Interior looking east

40.7 St Matthew (Megaw and Hawkins 1977)

41.1 Plan (after Papageorgiou 1963)

42.1 Plan. Phase 1 (after Manning 2002)

42.2 Plan. Phase 2 (after Manning 2002)

42.3 Apse of Phase 2 looking northeast

43.1 Site looking southeast

43.2 Transverse corridor looking south

43.3 Cruciform font looking southeast

43.4 East apse of chamber south of baptistery, looking west

44.1 West portal.
Proconnesian colonnettes

44.2 Iconostasis.
Proconnesian colonnettes

45.1 Plan (after Willis 1986)

45.2 *Opus sectile* pavement (Michaelides 1993)

46.1 Site looking east

46.2 Site looking northeast

47.1 Phase 1. Plan (after Megaw 1995)

47.2 Phase 2. Plan (after Papageorghiou 1986)

47.3 Central aisle
looking west

47.4 South colonnade of
nave looking southeast

47.5 Cipollino column from south colonnade. Drill holes probably marking the position of crosses

47.6 Proconnesian column

47.7 Carian column

47.8 Corinthian capitals

47.9 Foundation of free-standing apse looking north

47.10 Court, east of the free-standing apse, looking north

47.11 East court looking northwest

47.12 Central apse of Phase 2 looking south

47.13 North apsidiole of Phase 2 looking west

47.14 Detail of sixth-century pavement

47.15 Detail of sixth-century pavement

47.16 Detail of sixth-century pavement

47.17 Nave paving.
Phase 1 (mosaic) and
Phase 2 (*opus sectile*)
(Michaelides 1993)

47.18 Phase 2. Southern
inner aisle looking west

47.19 Phase 2. Paving of southern inner aisle looking west

47.20 Phase 2. Straight east wall of north outer aisle looking south

47.21 Narthex looking south

47.22 Descending pavements of the basilica, the narthex and the atrium looking northeast

47.23 Atrium looking northeast

47.24 Phiale atrium looking northwest

48.1 Plan (after Papageorgiou 1986)

48.2 Site looking southeast

48.3 Narthex looking south

48.4 Apse exterior looking southwest

48.5 Re-erected column on raised stylobate of north colonnade looking southeast

48.6 Mosaic pavement in south aisle looking east

49.1 Plan (Pallas 1977)

49.2 Baptistery pavement.
Detail (Michaelides 1987b)

49.3 Baptistery. Dedicatory inscription (Michaelides 1987b)

50.1 Plan (Giudice 2004)

50.2 Apses looking west

50.3 Apses looking south

50.4 Subterranean passage at the eastern limit of site looking north

51.1 Plan (after Papageorghiou 1986)

51 Peyia: Baptistery basilica

51.2 Baptistery looking northwest

51.3 Baptistery court looking southeast

51.4 Font looking south

51.5 Lotus border of baptistery court pavement

51.6 Baptistery basilica. Looking southeast

51.7 Baptistery basilica. North apsidiole looking southeast

51.8 Sockets for chancel screen posts. Bema, western edge, looking south

51.9 North colonnade, east end. T-shaped pier and respond against north wall

52.1 Plan (after Papageorgiou 1986)

52.2 Basilica looking east

52.3 Proconnesian column and Theodosian capital. South colonnade looking east

52.4 Theodosian capital

52.5 Central apse and synthronon looking east

52.6 Synthronon. Axial stairs looking east

52.7 Bema.
Mosaic pavement
looking east

52.8 Mosaic pavement
at the foot of the
synthronon.
Imbricated motif.
Looking northeast

52.9 Nave mosaic.
Animal panel
(Michaelides
1987b)

52.10 Atrium. Looking southeast

52.11 Atrium. Affronted beasts looking east

53.1 Plan (after Megaw 1974)

53.2 Three-sided central apse looking southwest

53.3 Central apse. Site of synthronon, looking east

53.4 Base and capital. North colonnade looking northeast

53.5 Possible treasury looking southwest

53.6 West portico and narthex looking northeast

54.1 Plan (after Megaw 1974)

54.2 Basilica, looking southeast

54.3 Central apse and synthronon looking east

54.4 Proconnesian base, column and capital. South colonnade looking southeast

54.5 Capital

54.6 Tomb at south end of narthex looking southeast

55.1 Plan (after Caraher 2011)

55.2 East end looking northwest

55.3 North aisle
looking west

55.4 Column fragment

55.5 Base

55.6 Theodosian capital.
Fragment

56.1 Plan (after Caraher 2011)

56.2 East end looking south

56.3 Burials in south aisle
looking east

56.4 Narthex looking south

59.1 Site looking east

59.2 Plan (after Megaw 1974)

59.3 Header and stretcher wallwork. Inner wall of south aisle

59.4 Basilica looking southeast

59.5 Nave looking west

59.6 South apsidiole looking east

59.7 South outer aisle
looking west

59.8 South outer aisle
looking west

59.9 Possible sacristy looking southwest

59.10 Site of east court looking east

59.11 Southern inter-wall passage looking north

59.12 Northern inter-wall passage looking north

59.13 Hammered limestone column drum. Nave, south colonnade

59.14 Capital. Nave, north colonnade

59.15 Outer aisle, south side. Pier with attached demi-shaft looking northwest

59.16 Outer aisle, north side. Pier with attached demi-shaft looking northeast

59.17 Outer aisle, south side. Possible position of intercolumnial screen

59.18 Pier with attached demi-shafts. Northeast opening to transverse aisle

59.19 Probable site of Epiphanius' tomb looking east

59.20 Apsidal-ended annex south of the baptistery, looking east

59.21 As 59.20 looking west (Michaelides 1992)

59.22 Phase 2. North aisle looking east

60.1 Plan (after Papageorgiou 1986)

60.2 East end of Late Antique and Middle Byzantine churches

60.3 North stylobate looking west

60.4 Central apse looking east

60.5 Bema paving.
Detail

60.6 Eastern respond
of south colonnade
looking southeast

60.7 North stylobate.
Routed base
looking northwest

60.8 Capitals, possibly from Late Antique basilica

60.9 East end of south aisle. *Mensa martyris* looking east

61.1 Site plan (after Roux 1998)

61.2 Plan (after Roux 1998)

61.3 Looking east from the western most atrium

61.4 Inner western atrium looking southeast

61.5 *Phiale* looking southeast

61.6 Funerary chapel in blocked south corridor looking east

61.7 Monumental staircase from port looking east

61.8 *Opus sectile* paving of bath complex looking east

61.9 Basilica looking east

61.10 Central apse and synthronon looking east

61.11 Detail of southern horseshoe-shaped apsidiole

61.12 *Kyklion* looking north

61.13 Axial recess in *kyklion* looking north

61.14 Inscribed cross opposite 61.12 looking east

61.15 Marble base supporting respond against the west wall looking northwest

61.16 Northeast respond. Cut half column. Looking southeast

61.17 North apsidiole. Reliquary looking east

61.18 Breccia coralline revetment in north apsidiole looking east

61.19 Proconnesian
revetment in
south apsidiole
looking east

61.20 'Baptistry'
looking east

61.21 West end of 'baptistry' and lobby looking west

62 Salmis: Forum basilica

62.1 Plan

62.2 Forum looking north

63.1 Site of sixth-century chapel looking east

63.2 Eastern shaft and circular cistern

64.1 Structure 3.
Mosaic pavement

64.2 Structure 3. Inscription beneath *bema* floor of Basilica B

64.3 Basilica A.
Central basin and
thalassa of eastern
feature looking south

64.4 Basilica A. Hypothetical plan (after Megaw 2001 and Neal 2010)

64.5 Basilica A.
Position of posts on
north side of the nave
looking east

64.6 Basilica A.
North wall? Stairwell in
north aisle looking east

64.7 Basilica A. Central basin and *thalassa* looking southeast

64.8 Basilica A. Posts and enclosure of sanctuary looking east

64.9 Basilica A. Waterfowl. North inner aisle

64.10 Basilica A. Dolphin. North inner aisle

64.11 Basilica A.
Swan. North
inner aisle

64.12 Basilica A.
Cross motif.
South outer aisle
looking north

64.13 Basilica A. South inner aisle looking north

64.14 Basilica B. Plan (after des Gagnier and Tinh 1985)

64.15 Basilica B.
Apse looking
southeast

64.16 Basilica B.
Passage between
the north apsidiole
and the central
apse looking south

64.17 Basilica B.
Passage between the
central apse and the south
apsidole looking south

64.18 Basilica B.
The turn from the *kyklion*
into the passage leading
to the south apsidole
looking east

64.19 Basilica B. North apsidiole looking west

64.20 Basilica B. Column. South aisle looking east

64.21 Basilica B. Header and stretcher wallwork on the north side looking south

64.22 Basilica B. Circular niche in north wall

64.23 Basilica B.
Rectangular
niche in
south wall

64.24 Basilica B. *Kyklion*. Looking southeast

64.25 Basilica B.
The turn from the *kyklion* into the passage leading to the south apsidiole looking southwest

64.26 Basilica B. Annex between north aisle and the northern exedra of narthex

64.27 Basilica B. Angle of the south and the east porticoes of the atrium looking west

64.28 Basilica B. Northern exedra of the narthex looking northwest

64.29 Basilica B. Detail of southern exedra of the narthex looking southwest

64.30 Basilica B. North entrance to the atrium looking south

64.31 Basilica B. Window head of south exedra of the narthex looking southwest

64.32 Basilica B. Atrium. North portico. Bench looking northwest

66.1 Plan (after Megaw 1946)

66.2 Site looking west

66.3 Central apse looking north

66.4 Limestone column

66.5 Northwest respond embedded in masonry of later pier basilica, looking northeast

66.6 Southeast respond embedded in masonry of later pier basilica, looking south

66.7 Northeast respond looking northeast

66.8 Proconessian furnishings (Megaw 1946)

67.1 Synthronon looking east

67.2 Bema. *Opus sectile* panel

69.1 Bema (Foulias 2012)

69.2 Bema mosaic (Foulias 2012)

69.3 Bema mosaic. Standing lioness (Foulias 2012)

69.4 Bema mosaic. Cuttlefish (Foulias 2012)

69.5 Nave pavement.
Detail (Foulias 2012)

69.6 Nave pavement.
Detail (Foulias 2012)

71.1 Plan (Papageorgiou 1966)

71.2 Dedicatory inscription (Michaelides 1987b)

